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**QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF CLASSROOM ILLUMINANCE: A CASE STUDY OF
CTU MOALBOAL CAMPUS, COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING**

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ABSTRACT

Title : Quality Assessment of Classroom Illuminance: A Case Study of CTU Moalboal Campus, College of Engineering

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Illuminance quality is essential for effective learning environments, significantly impacting students' visual comfort, concentration, and academic performance. Defined as the amount of light reaching a surface and measured in lux, illuminance is influenced by various factors, particularly natural light sources and artificial lighting. This study undertakes to assess the illuminance quality in classrooms at the College of Engineering Department, Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus, focusing on enhancing occupant comfort. Classroom assessments were conducted in March 2024, measuring illuminance levels, uniformity, and wall surface reflectance using a lux meter. Data were analyzed using ANOVA to identify significant differences and were aligned with established standards through a Normal Distribution (Bell Curve). Results indicated that Room 2 had the highest illuminance level, while Room 1 had the lowest. Room 5 demonstrated strong compliance with standards, whereas Rooms 1 and 2 fell short. In particular, Room 2 also displayed low illuminance uniformity, revealing uneven light distribution. The assessment underscores the need for improved lighting in Rooms 1 and 2 to enhance visual comfort. Differences in wall surface reflectance were observed, with Rooms 3 and 5 exhibiting lower values potentially influenced by curtain color and furniture arrangement. Recommendations include upgrading fixtures, optimizing furniture arrangements, and using brighter wall colors to foster a visually comfortable learning environment.

Keywords: *Illuminance Level, Illuminance Uniformity, Surface Reflectance, Visual*

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CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

In some educational infrastructures, the appropriate way of lighting up classrooms and offices matters more than it is to be thought of. It is not always about how everything is to be seen clearly; it relatively impacts how students feel towards themselves and the institution they are in, the sharpness and focus of their minds, and even how active they are academically. Thus, an increase in classroom illumination can create a conducive environment for the students that will motivate them to concentrate (Oribó, 2021). On the basis of some of the general guidelines for lighting in academic spaces, there is more that we don't know yet. It is important to conduct a thorough investigation, considering factors such as the academic level of students, to expand understanding beyond existing common guidelines for lighting in academic spaces.

The classroom environment can be considered an integrated and complex system that involves essential aspects such as physical layout, interior design, infrastructure, furniture, and equipment. Also, exposure to external environmental factors such as daylight, weather conditions, and air quality has a critical but very complicated impact on students' comfort and wellbeing (Al-Horr et al., 2016). Specifically, the illuminance quality in a learning environment is believed to be one of the most critical factors among all environmental aspects in the classroom. Although its significance is generally recognized, knowledge about the appropriate and most efficient settings of illumination for various

educational environments and practices is still insufficient and sometimes controversial (Sun, 2021).

For the past years, the educational system all throughout the world has evolved, changing its forms and methods of education in order to prepare students for the standards of Industry 5.0 (Marinic & Pecina, 2023). Students now spend an average of 12 hours a day in school, including programs or activities for promoting knowledge among students (Melis et al., 2021). Many factors may affect the performance of the students, and this includes the illuminance of the classroom. Illuminance is the measurement of how much light illuminates a given surface area. Assessing the illuminance quality of the classroom is vital to (i) know how much light must be set as a standard for every state university classroom in order for the students to be mentally active and (ii) know what type of light (warm or cold) affects the performance of the students. Comfort in the learning environment is considered in every educational sector, such that students must be in a zone where they are prepared and ready to take part in discussions and other certain tasks. Through evaluating and selecting appropriate light sources based on the specific requirements of the classrooms, considering factors such as energy efficiency, color temperature, and longevity, we can promote sustainable lighting practices and cost-effective solutions. Also, to optimize the lighting layout and design in the classrooms, considering the spatial configuration, furniture arrangement, and natural light integration, to create a well-balanced and visually comfortable environment that enhances the overall learning experience for students.

Hence, the Philippine's sector for education, mainly the Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), have inconsistently

addressed this matter, and through research and further observations, an immediate response can be requested on the students' behalf to experience quality education. A related study conducted at Mapua University in the Philippines showed that different illuminance levels (low, medium, and high) have a significant effect on the students' cognitive performance (Bautista et al., 2022).

Creating environments that support learning excellence becomes crucial since universities all over the world serve as hubs of learning and knowledge dissemination. Buildings, occupant needs, and environmental factors must all be integrated during the complex process of architectural design (Jafari et al., 2021). This process needs special consideration because it is essential to creating sustainable structures that meet the needs of their learners in all aspects of individuals who want to be educationally inclined and capable, particularly when it comes to educational buildings because the architecture directly influences children's learning capacities.

Thus, this study purposely aims to conduct a comprehensive assessment of illuminance quality in the newly constructed classrooms of the CTU Moalboal Campus, identify areas for improvement and potential shortcomings, and develop strategies for enhancing the lighting conditions in the CTU Moalboal Campus new building classrooms, with an emphasis on enhancing visual comfort that ultimately fosters an environment conducive to optimal learning outcomes that potentially enhances student well-being and academic performance. Specifically, consider relevant factors such as illuminance levels, illuminance uniformity, and surface reflectance to ensure an optimal learning environment for educational building occupants.

Theoretical Background

This study was anchored on Walberg's theory of Educational Productivity, the Vitruvius' Daylight Quality Theory, and international standard development organizations for illumination.

Calleb and Simion (2021) utilize the tenets of **Walberg's (1981) theory of Educational Productivity** in assessing the effects of artificial classroom illumination. This theory hypothesizes that the proximate environment and individual psychological characteristics of students have an impact on the educational process's cognitive and behavioral results. It examines variables at optimal levels, including students' prior achievement/ability, age, motivation/perseverance on learning tasks, and class/school environment factors. This theory is considered an educational process goal: to enhance the learning environment as a means of increasing educational productivity. Based on the study of Calleb and Simion (2021), the improvement of artificial classroom lighting will improve students' psychological environment, and this will improve students' task concentration and academic performance. Thus, it particularly implies that adequate classroom illumination significantly contributes to establishing a conducive learning environment.

The ability of an educational building's structure to contribute to the creation of an optimal learning environment necessitates consideration of its structure in the assessment of illuminance quality for increased visual comfort in classrooms. Urech (2021) introduces the **Daylight Quality Theory of Vitruvius**, which emphasizes that optimal luminous ambiance satisfaction can be attained by incorporating the three key facets of architecture: Venustas (beauty), Utilitas (utility), and Firmitas (durability). This

hypothesis also takes into account other factors, including sun orientation, weather conditions, and natural light sources. Significantly, it does not only focus on visual needs and comfort alone but also addresses the satisfaction of social interactions, performance, health, and safety matters (Cauwerts & Piderit, 2018).

Understanding how daylighting affects student performance will lead to an understanding of classroom layout designs, regulations, standards, and guidelines. Light provides the necessary amount of illumination to allow any work, including writing and reading, to be accomplished effectively. Daylight impacts circadian rhythm and biological clock, as well as human sleeping patterns and timetables. The biological conditions of the students are likewise not an exception. Effective daylighting in the classroom ameliorates the educational setting for the well-being of the students' health and academic performance, in addition to being energy efficient (Le et al., 2016; Al-Ashwal & Hassan, 2018).

Natural daylight sources and artificial lighting have the same impacts known as the 'Triple Effect', which are visual functions, creating biological effects, and emotional perceptions (Arabi et al., 2018). The Daylight Quality Theory also adapts the first two lighting quality requirements, which are visual performance and post-visual performance for students. The increase in visual discomfort in learning environments and lighting aspects such as shadows, uniformity of light distribution, glare, and reflection must be considered. Indoor lighting in general gives an impact to the occupants' desire and satisfaction to do specific work tasks (Husini, 2016).

The conviction that lighting in a learning environment has a substantial impact on comfort, productivity, and the user's health is now well established. Thus, the International

Commission on Illumination (CIE) has shifted its focus from visual illumination in favor of a more inclusive definition of illuminance quality that takes into account human needs, architectural integration, and economic constraints such as energy consumption (Liu et al., 2020). Also, and various international standard development organization including Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment, International Organization for Standardization/ International Electrotechnical Commission and Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineer, significantly alter lighting practice. The scope of the standard covers the lighting requirements by providing recommended design illuminances for different locations in educational areas, enabling individuals to perform visual tasks efficiently with comfort and safety.

Adequate illumination necessitates equal consideration for lighting amount and quality. In this standard, it allows to take the stated values for various work areas and task types, including not only the illuminance but also the source's limiting discomfort glare and minimum color rendering index. The necessary parameters to be used in this study, aiming to create a comfortable visual learning environment, are proposed in the body of this standard. The recommended values are thought to strike an acceptable balance between the requirements for a safe, healthy, and optimal learning environment. Moreover, the visual ergonomic parameters such as perceptual ability and the characteristics and attributes of the task are presented, which determine the quality of the user's visual perception.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

The integration of Walberg's Theory of Educational Productivity and Vitruvius' Daylight Quality Theory allows for a comprehensive approach to illuminance quality assessment that takes both artificial and natural lighting aspects into account. This reinforces the robustness and comprehensiveness of this study's methodological plan. The integration ensures that the study's methodology not only evaluates the technical aspects of illumination but also considers relevant parameters influencing visual comfort. Furthermore, Vitruvius' theory accentuates the significance of natural daylight and the attributes of *fiumitas*, *utilitas*, and *venustas* in building design. Integrating these concepts will make a substantial contribution to the creation of functional classroom settings suited to increased learning experiences, with a focus on visual comfort.

Moreover, the incorporation of various international standards for illumination into the study's methodology adds an important degree of legitimacy and reliability to the assessment process. By adhering to globally recognized standards, the study's methodological plan ensures a systematic and standardized evaluation of illuminance quality, enabling a comprehensive analysis of lighting parameters within the CTU Moalboal Campus new building classrooms. This conformity with international standards strengthens the methodological plan's validity and applicability, enabling a more robust and accurate assessment of illuminance quality that can serve as a benchmark for ensuring optimal lighting conditions and enhanced visual comfort in the educational setting.

In general, illumination in the classroom is typically comprised of daylight and artificial light. However, their individual features and availability make the usual classroom illuminant setting dependent on artificial light and take advantage of daylight as much as

possible. Related research has reached consensus that daylight is not only preferred by teachers and students but also reduces the risk of myopia (Ballina, 2016). However, daylight features variability in amount, spectrum, and distribution due to time, weather, and sitting, which cannot solely support activities in the classroom. In most cases, artificial light dominates indoor illuminance, while daylight acts as a supplementary light source (Sun, 2021).

The comprehensive classroom illuminance quality assessment method integrates the measurement of crucial factors within the illuminance context, including the evaluation of daylight exposure and its interaction with the classroom environment, as well as an in-depth analysis of the function of the artificial lighting systems to ensure consistent and appropriate illumination levels. Evaluating the illuminance distribution across the classroom space effectively measures the illuminance uniformity and identifies potential areas of over- or under-illumination, enabling the optimization of lighting arrangements to enhance overall visual comfort and learning efficiency. Furthermore, the assessment of surface reflectance and its consistency under specific and various lighting conditions plays a crucial role in determining the accuracy and vibrancy of visual perception.

In particular, the assessment method is tailored to evaluate the illuminance quality within the classroom environment, centered on four key parameters: illuminance level, illuminance uniformity, glare, and surface reflectance. The International Commission on Illumination (CIE) documents standards on lighting environments, relevant codes, and available research results specifying or recognizing the aforementioned parameters as relevant for visual comfort in indoor lighting (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021). Addressing these fundamental visual comfort factors emphasizes the importance of

creating an optimal learning environment. Each parameter plays a crucial role in determining the lighting conditions and their potential impact on the physiological and psychological well-being of educational building occupants. Specifically, illuminance level is fundamental to ensuring an adequate amount of light for various visual tasks, contributing to optimal visibility, and preventing visual strain. Simultaneously, illuminance uniformity addresses the consistent distribution of light across the classroom, minimizing areas of glare and shadows that could otherwise lead to discomfort or distraction. Moreover, glare, as a key parameter, is significant in mitigating potential discomfort caused by excessive brightness variations or direct glare sources. Surface reflectance, the fourth parameter under consideration, influences the perception of brightness and color in the classroom. Understanding and optimizing surface reflectance contributes to creating a visually balanced and comfortable space, impacting the overall ambiance, and supporting the learning process. In essence, investigating these four recognized relevant parameters collectively ensures a holistic approach to improving visual comfort (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021).

In the context of determining classroom specifications and assessing environmental Contextual Factors such as Weather Conditions and Time of Day, a thorough examination is imperative for creating an optimal learning environment (Ashrafian, 2023). Each of the classroom specifications holds significant influence over the dynamics of the learning environment. The dimensions of the classroom, denoted by its size and layout, directly impact the spatial arrangement and overall accessibility. An optimal layout can facilitate effective engagement and interaction among students and the instructor, contributing to a positive learning atmosphere. Seat capacity is a critical

aspect of determining the number of students the classroom can accommodate. This specification is pivotal in maintaining a balance between a conducive learning environment and the practical limitations of the physical space. Window characteristics, such as size, design, and transparency, play a crucial role in controlling natural light, ventilation, and external views within the classroom. An effective evaluation of these characteristics ensures an appropriate balance, avoiding insufficient lighting that may affect students' visual comfort. The orientation of windows and doors further influences the distribution of natural light and the overall flow of the classroom environment. An optimal window and door orientation can enhance the ambient lighting conditions and contribute to a more comfortable and inviting space for learning.

Simultaneously, the assessment of Environmental Contextual Factors, specifically Weather Conditions and Time of Day, is crucial. Weather conditions can impact natural lighting, temperature, and overall comfort within the classroom. Understanding and adapting to these factors enables the creation of an environment that accommodates different seasons and weather patterns. Additionally, considering the Time of Day is essential, as lighting needs and the overall atmosphere within the classroom can vary throughout the day. This assessment aids in implementing lighting strategies and environmental adjustments that align with the specific needs of students at different times.

The inclusion of weather conditions, along with the date and time of the assessment, holds significant value in ensuring a comprehensive and reliable analysis of the lighting environment within the classroom setting. Incorporating weather data enables a thorough examination of how external factors, such as cloud cover, sunlight intensity, and seasonal fluctuations, influence the illuminance quality within the classroom.

Determining these weather-related variations contributes to analyzing the interplay between natural and artificial lighting sources, facilitating informed decisions on lighting adjustments that can optimize the learning environment despite changes in external light conditions. Concurrently, the date and time of the assessment enable the identification of temporal patterns in illuminance levels throughout the day and across different weather conditions (Brown et al., 2022).

Gathering the data with various times and dates, one can discern how the shifting daylight conditions impact the overall lighting dynamics within the classroom. This temporal analysis provides crucial insights into how variations in lighting might affect students' visual comfort, circadian rhythms, and overall well-being, thereby enabling the implementation of lighting strategies that align with natural daily rhythms and seasonal changes to foster a conducive and supportive learning environment (Amundadottir et al., 2016).

Therefore, considering both the weather conditions and the date and time of the assessment, this study's methodological plan will encompass a holistic approach to evaluating illuminance quality, accounting for the dynamic nature of lighting variations and their potential impact on students' learning experiences. This comprehensive analysis will ultimately contribute to the development of tailored lighting solutions that prioritize enhanced visual comfort and promote an optimal learning environment for students, regardless of external environmental fluctuations.

In terms of methodology, the dominant tools used for gathering data are lux meters, which are used to measure the light level inside the classroom. An observation form is also used to record the data in each sample. This form is used to avoid recording

the wrong reading of the light level. A decade later, the exploration of the potential connection between fluorescent luminaires with varying spectral ranges and intensities of illumination in classrooms and human health was started. Today, many educational institutions have changed the usual classroom furniture layouts, which has prompted studies on how lighting should be constructed in response. Therefore, an additional variable pertaining to space features was present. The combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies increases, specifically, regarding the use of both measurement-based practices, such as illuminance levels, spectral distribution, and daylight analysis, as well as methods dealing with the users' feedback and evaluation of the space, such as questionnaires and tests for students. Although some studies rely entirely on simulation software for spatial assessment and light-level calculations, a limited but considerable number of examples re-introduce user-based techniques for spatial evaluation (Angelaki et al., 2022). This indicates that the evaluation and design processes did not incorporate user feedback; rather, the software's calculations in response to the guidelines in effect at the time of the study served as the sole basis for the ideas.

The illuminance quality is often limited to measuring and comparing the illuminance levels of certain tasks. However, lighting quality and attaining adequate levels of visual comfort are strongly dependent on other factors that cannot be disregarded in a detailed analysis. Therefore, the appropriate method to be used for assessing lighting quality remains a subject of discussion in the scientific community since it is often limited to the evaluation of the quantity of light (Kruisselbrink et al., 2018). These methods, in particular, are commonly dependent on the illuminance levels, which are those of less recent

development yet provide relevant information, but they are limited to the average conditions in the specified task areas. Additionally, alternatives for assessing illuminance quality, such as administering questionnaires, must be established in order to thoroughly evaluate the subjective perception of visual comfort in a learning environment (Castilla et al., 2017). In the scientific community, it is now common opinion that illumination quality should be assessed using a holistic approach in which multiple factors must be crucially considered (Rocca et al., 2020; Kruisselbrink et al., 2018).

Thus, upon revisiting the theories, related literature, and studies on assessing the illuminance quality of a learning environment, as well as the foundational standards for illuminance levels and other related factors to ensure a systematic and standardized assessment, the researcher aimed to evaluate classrooms to potentially enhance students' visual comfort within the classroom environment.

Review of Related Literature

In the realm of higher educational institutions, the significance of illuminance quality transcends the conventional role of lighting as a functional necessity. According to Seman et al. (2020), lighting is one of the energies that stimulates the human sense of vision and includes both artificial light sources and natural interior illumination from daylight. Typically, people spend the majority of their time indoors, whether in school, the office, or their homes, and thus the indoor environment indeed impacts a human's health, performance, and well-being. As highlighted by the study by Seman et al. (2020), individuals spent over 80% of their daily time indoors compared to outdoor. The occupants of the educational building are spending more time indoors by carrying out various activities such as reading, writing, and various means of learning and working. Hence, illuminance quality, as characterized by the intensity and distribution of light within educational spaces, emerges as one of the critical determinants of the overall learning environment. An adequate illuminance quality significantly contributes to psychological and physiological benefits and improves the occupant's wellbeing, health, and safety. For that reason, the indoor lighting should be maintained at the optimum level, whose illuminance quality profoundly influences the visual comfort experienced by students and educators, shaping their well-being and engagement within the classroom.

According to Vilcekova et al. (2017), lighting quality plays a significant role in a good IEQ (Indoor Environmental Quality) in classrooms, and it is crucial for students' learning. Several studies have also revealed a variety of issues with the lighting in existing classrooms. In the scientific community, the assessment methods of lighting quality are still subject to discussion because they are often limited to the evaluation of the quantity

of light (illuminance and luminance) (Kruisselbrink et al., 2018). Particularly, the lighting quality assessment methods based on illuminance levels are those of less recent development and provide relevant information, but they are limited to the average conditions in the task areas. Thus, the illuminance quality and the achievement of adequate levels of visual comfort strongly depend on other factors that cannot be neglected in a detailed analysis (e.g., luminance distribution, glare, color rendition, daylight availability, circadian and flicker effects, etc.) (Leccese et al., 2020)

Visual comfort is generally defined as a subjective response to the amount and quality of light present in a specific space at a given time. Although there is no universally accepted definition of human comfort, various metrics have been developed to quantify users' appreciation of their environments, objects, or interfaces. Both insufficient and excessive lighting can lead to visual discomfort (Gale et al., 2011). Identifying a comfortable environment is relatively straightforward; however, describing a visually comfortable space presents a challenge, as it encompasses a general sense of well-being and satisfaction rather than a singular measurable effect. Typically, individuals experience minimal visual discomfort in well-lit environment. The International Commission on Illumination (CIE) has established standards for lighting environments, recognizing key parameters critical to visual comfort in indoor settings, including illuminance, surface reflectance, uniformity ratio, and glare (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021).

Numerous standards have been established across the world and by various organizations, emphasizing lighting quality, energy efficiency, and sustainability to create learning environments that encourage academic performance while promoting well-

being. These guidelines take a holistic approach to addressing the sustainability and functional aspects of lighting design, ensuring a balance between energy efficiency, overall well-being, and visual comfort.

Illuminance refers to the quantity of light that illuminates a surface, measured in lux. It represents the total luminous flux incident on a surface per unit area (lumen per m²). The distribution of illuminance within the task area and its surrounding environment significantly influences the safety, and comfort with which an individual perceives and performs visual tasks (NSAI Standard, 2011). Numerous codes and standards delineate the minimum illuminance levels required for the task area on the reference surface. The average illuminance must not drop below the recommended values (measured in lux).

Table 1. Summary of Recommended Illuminance Levels for Classroom

Source	Range
EN 12464-1	500 lux Immediate surrounding illuminance: 300 lux Background area illuminance: 100 lux
NBC 2016	300 – 500lux
GRIHA V – 2015	300 - 500 lux
The WELL Building Standards	300–500 lux if ambient lighting ≤ 300 lux
CIBSE Code for lighting	300 lux: mainly screen-based tasks 500 lux: paper-based tasks

Table 1 summarizes the recommended illuminance levels for various indoor environments as outlined by several established standards (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021). These recommendations highlight the optimal lux levels needed for different areas and activities, ensuring that spaces are adequately lit to enhance visual comfort and performance. The sources include recognized guidelines such as EN 12464-1, NBC 2016, GRIHA V - 2015, The WELL Building Standards, and the CIBSE Code for Lighting, each providing a range of illuminance levels tailored to specific tasks and settings.

The Illuminance Level in classrooms plays a critical role in determining the quality of lighting, which directly impacts student's visual comfort and academic performance. The GRIHA V-2015 (Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment) which is India's national rating system for sustainable buildings, emphasizes energy-efficient lighting in educational spaces. It recommends maintaining illuminance levels between 300-500-750 lux, which ensures visual comfort while also enhancing the learning experiences. This recommendation complies with the findings of Yang et al. (2020), where appropriate illuminance and correlated color temperature (CCT) were found to positively influence cognitive performance, especially in areas of visual perception and memory tasks. The implementation of this standard supports a balanced approach that prioritizes both student well-being and sustainability by optimizing light for both functional and environmental needs.

Uniformity ratio is crucial for enhancing user perception, visual acuity, and overall visibility. In discussing light uniformity within a given area, the focus is on the task area encompassing both the objects and their immediate surroundings. According to NSAI

Standards (2011), the uniformity ratio is defined as the ratio of minimum to average illuminance in the visual task area. An optimal working environment is one in which occupants do not perceive varying lighting levels with the naked eye and experience a well-distributed light environment. A higher uniformity ratio indicates better uniformity, contributing to greater comfort for individuals.

Table 2. Summary of Recommended Illuminance Uniformity for Classroom

Source	Illuminance uniformity over task
ASHRAE 90.1	$U_{O, min} = 0.7$
CIBSE	$U_{O, min} = 0.6$
ISO/CIE 8995	$U_{O, min} = 0.7$
EN 12464-1	$U_{O, average} \geq 0.7$
AS 1680	$U_{O, average} > 0.67$
DIN 5035	$U_{O, average} > 0.67$
NSVV	$U_{O, average} > 0.7$
BS 8206-1	$U_{O, average} > 0.8$ $U_{O, max} > 0.7$

Table 2 summarizes the recommended illuminance uniformity ratios for indoor spaces, as specified by various standards (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021). Uniformity in lighting is essential for maintaining consistent visual conditions across work areas. The sources listed include ASHRAE 90.1, CIBSE, ISO/CIE 8995, EN 12464-1, AS 1680, DIN 5035, NSVV, and BS 8206-1, each providing guidelines for achieving optimal lighting quality. Each source specifies minimum or average uniformity values to achieve optimal lighting quality

The Illuminance alone is not enough to guarantee optimal visual conditions. The illuminance uniformity of the light distribution is equally important for creating visually comfortable space. The ISO/CIE 8995 (International Organization for Standardization/ International Electrotechnical Commission), a globally recognized standard, highlights the importance of uniformity in lighting for maintaining consistent visual comfort. This standard specifies that a minimum uniformity ratio of 0.7 should be maintained in classrooms, which is essential for supporting visual tasks without causing eye strain or fatigue. The uniformity ratio is calculated using the formula $U_0 = \frac{E_{min}}{E_{average}}$, where E_{min} is the minimum illuminance and $E_{average}$ is the average illuminance across the space. This consistent distribution plays a critical role in visual comfort and academic performance, as evidenced in studies of Tureková et al. (2018), which emphasize the importance of lighting uniformity in preventing visual fatigue.

Surface Reflectance contributes to a balanced distribution of luminance. When reflectance exceeds the desired range, it leads to elevated luminance levels, potentially causing glare. Conversely, if reflectance falls below the preferred range, it results in diminished luminance, creating a lackluster and uninspiring work environment. The degree of reflectance is influenced by several factors, with the finishes and paints applied to the walls being particularly significant in determining overall reflectance (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021).

Table 3: Summary of Recommended Wall Surface Reflectance for Classroom

Codes/Rating System	Range
	Walls
EN 12464-1	0.5-0.8
CIBSE Code for Lighting	0.5-0.8
LEED V4.1 Interior Design	60%
The WELL Building Standards v 1 with May 2016 addenda	≥0.7

Table 3 presents the recommended surface reflectance ranges for walls as specified by various standard codes and rating systems (The Energy and Resources Institute, 2021). Surface reflectance plays a critical role in enhancing overall lighting quality and energy efficiency within indoor spaces. The guidelines provided by sources such as EN 12464-1, the CIBSE Code for Lighting, LEED V4.1 Interior Design, and The WELL Building Standards v1 with May 2016 addenda serve as benchmarks for achieving optimal visual comfort and sustainability in design.

Surface reflectance is another key factor that contributes to lighting quality. It is the ratio of luminous flux reflected by a body (with or without diffusion) to the flux it receives (National Building Code of India, Volume 2, 2016). The CIBSE (Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers) Code for Lighting specifies that surfaces, especially walls, should have reflectance values between 0.5 and 0.8 to optimize light distribution within a space. This ensures that natural and artificial lighting are used effectively to create a well-lit environment, reducing the need for additional lighting and thus promoting energy efficiency. In this study, surface reflectance is calculated using the formula $\rho = E_r/E_i$,

where E_r is the reflected illuminance and E_i is the incident illuminance. This method, proposed by Jupp (1997), is a cost-effective alternative to using expensive luminance meters and complies with the standards set by CIBSE and EN 12464-1.

The assessment of the quality of illumination, traditional tools measuring luminance and illuminance levels point-to-point are commonly employed; however, these traditional tools are typically associated with high costs. In this sense, the study conducted by Ibañez et al. (2017) utilized the use of photographs, which become an optional tool to capture the values of luminance and permit the development of quick and cheap studies in relation to traditional forms of evaluation. The visual comfort of a technical drawing (project) classroom was analysed by on-site measurements and by means of HDR (High Dynamic Range) pictures. Initially, room details were drawn; subsequently, measurements of illuminance levels were performed and values were obtained comparing with the Brazilian code NBR 15215-4 for different hours using a digital lux meter model THDL400. At the same time, images of the room were captured for different exposure values using a Reflex camera, a digital Canon 600D, a wide-angle lens (10–18 mm), and a tripod. The classroom presents glare problems near the windows. The results indicate the need for changes in internal surfaces (walls and ceilings), light fixture repositioning, and the use of strategies that allow a better distribution of lighting.

In accordance with the aforementioned context, the study conducted by Reda et al. (2021) evaluate the effect of luminaries' arrangement and type on visual comfort and energy consumption. Two identical classrooms with differing luminaries' arrangements were selected to assess the efficacy of the existing lighting system in terms of illuminance uniformity, unified glare rating, and installed load efficacy ratio. The validation of DIALux

Evo software against measured illuminance facilitated the examination of suggested luminaries' arrangements and the replacement of existing fluorescent lamps with LED types to recommend an optimal scenario.

According to the study findings, the arrangement and type of luminaries are decisive factors influencing visual comfort and energy conservation. Consequently, the recommendation is to distribute luminaries in a way that aligns the number of rows with the number of columns, with the longitudinal length of the luminaire parallel to the illuminated space's longitudinal length. Field measurements indicated that the current lighting system does not offer visual comfort for occupants. According to simulation findings, the use of LED luminaries in classrooms is recommended to ensure visual comfort and achieve up to a 50% reduction in energy wastage. This recommendation aligns with the imperative identified in the study by Ibañez et al. (2017) for changes in internal surfaces, light fixture repositioning, and strategic lighting distribution.

Natural and Artificial Lighting

The quantity of lighting necessary in a given space is significantly determined by the availability of light. In instances where daylight is insufficient, the choice of additional lighting becomes imperative. Typically, this is achieved through the use of artificial light, designed to emulate daylight both in terms of colour temperature and light intensity. While the optimal illumination levels may vary based on the nature of visual tasks, it is essential to integrate a combination of artificial and natural light sources. According to Azodo et al. (2019), to achieve a well-balanced lighting design for educational facilities, both natural

and artificial lighting should be adequately calibrated to meet the illuminance requirements of the designated task spaces.

In the study conducted by Caner et al. (2016), the current daylighting conditions were analysed in terms of luminous comfort in the classrooms of Balikesir University in Turkey. This was managed through a questionnaire survey and numerical simulations in 16 different classrooms of the Faculty of Engineering-Architecture. The simulation study considered the differences in the performance parameters daylighting level, illuminance uniformity and daylighting factors in order to compare them with the values defined in the standards. Collected for the survey were 818 questionnaires, and these were analysed to understand the students' perception of luminous comfort in classrooms by using SPSS 22.0 and Minitab 16. The results of the simulation indicated that performance factors in all classrooms fell below standard values. Consequently, a combined approach of daylighting and artificial lighting may be essential, contingent on the distance from windows. This outcome underscores the importance of artificial lighting design, highlighting its significance on par with classroom design. According to survey findings, luminous comfort perception is primarily influenced by factors such as orientation, proximity to windows, and gender differences. Additionally, students expressed a preference for both natural and artificial lighting, aligning closely with the simulation results.

In practical scenarios, certain applications and buildings significantly rely on artificial lighting rather than daylight. This is notably observed in environments such as museums, conference rooms, and galleries. However, daylight holds a fundamental and irreplaceable significance in human life (Tureková et al., 2018) Hence, certain structures

lack access to daylight in substantial portions of their interior spaces, attributed to factors such as location, orientation, poor design, and functionality.

According to Pratiwi et al. (2022), the most important factors in maximizing natural lighting are facade design, window openings, and building orientation. The study assessed the quality of natural lighting in the SMA Negeri (SMAN)/ Public High school 6 DKI Jakarta school building and examined how the design of window openings and facades affects lighting quality and how current classroom design conditions affect students' comfort while carrying out learning activities. The analysis in this study uses the DIALux software to simulate and measure the level of natural lighting in classroom and laboratory. Findings from the research conducted, it was found that the condition of classrooms in SMAN 6 which planning is not optimal, in terms of orientation, the sides are still blocked, glare and incoming heat radiation. Although natural lighting is good enough, it cannot be denied that for the visual comfort of the classroom, artificial lighting is needed. Design factors such as the positioning of window height, student height, and various interior attributes contribute to diminished visual comfort in the classroom. Identified conditions encompass issues like glare, the selection of wall colors, and the use of curtains that obstruct the entry of natural lighting.

Moreover, the study by Makaremi et al. (2018) indicates that the type of luminaire is the most decisive parameter in the quantity and quality of light in an indoor environment. However, increasing indoor surface reflectance plays a key role in improving energy efficiency and visual comfort. The study investigated the effects of applying different design strategies on lighting energy use and visual comfort levels, considering variables such as surface finishing reflectance, type, number, and mounting height of luminaires.

Additionally, the study adopted Lighting design software DIALux evo 7.0, which provides simulations of a real-scale room according to different scenarios. The models were calibrated and validated using experimental field data. The results demonstrate the possibility of achieving electrical energy savings of up to 45% by enhancing surface reflectance properties. In conclusion, optimizing surface reflectance alongside luminaire selection can significantly contribute to energy efficiency and visual comfort in indoor environments.

The utilization of light-emitting diodes (LEDs) has witnessed a substantial paradigm shift in interior lighting within educational settings. Formerly, traditional lighting sources such as incandescent bulbs and fluorescent lights predominated, but over time, LEDs have progressively gained prominence. According to Morrow et al. (2018), LED (light-emitting diodes) became very popular because of their efficiency, longevity, and ability to provide a full, smooth, unbroken spectrum. A study conducted by Morrow et al. (2018) showed the impacts of fluorescent and LED lighting on students' attitudes and behavior in the classroom. Morrow et al. studied pre-K through high school qualified teachers from three schools and/or personal contacts of the principal investigator. Using survey data, they found that higher correlated color temperature lighting positively impacted alertness, attitude, and energy levels. The findings indicate that the ability to modulate light levels throughout the day has a beneficial effect on students' behavior and mood, providing valuable insights into the broader concept of interior lighting and its nuanced effects on students' non-visual performance. However, it is important to acknowledge the subjective nature of these findings, necessitating further research for a more comprehensive understanding.

Students' Visual and Non-Visual Performance

Classroom illuminance stands as a critical element with significant implications for students' academic performance and overall well-being within educational settings. The quality and type of light, whether artificial or natural, exert a direct and influential effect on the learning processes of students. It is necessary, however, to recognize the limitations of what we know at the current stage (Boyce, 2016). Regarding the visual effects of lighting, we have significant knowledge about how light affects our visual capabilities and perception. Concerning the non-visual effects, there is a suspicion that many parts of the human body are influenced by light, yet these areas remain relatively unexplored (Bodrogi et al., 2017). Thus, as has been emphasized by many researchers a full range of lighting research, encompassing both visual and non-visual domains, is still needed.

In the field study of Liu et al. (2020), a series of psychophysical tests were conducted to investigate the impact of indoor lighting on students' visual perception and cognitive performance. The two separate experiments conducted in a standard classroom at Wuhan University (China), tubular light-emitting diode (LED) sources and LED panel sources were installed. Seventy-nine college students participated in visual tests under these two lighting environments. The tests included evaluations of color preferences for fruits, vegetables, and skin tone, perceptual judgments on the lighting environment's atmosphere, assessments of reading comfort with different paper colors, a Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS) test to quantify alertness, and an Anfimov test of attention, which also considered paper colors. These tests were conducted before and after a two-hour self-study session under each lighting condition to explore the impact of visual fatigue on visual perception and cognitive performance.

The results revealed that indoor lighting significantly influenced atmosphere perception. However, no observable effects of lighting were detected on participants' alertness and attention. Intriguingly, visual fatigue was found to be insignificant in this context. Notably, the color of the paper, rather than indoor lighting, exhibited a significant impact on the visual comfort of reading text. Additionally, the participants' proficiency level significantly influenced the proofreading speed and accuracy in the Anfimov test, suggesting its relevance in similar studies. These initial findings from the field study contribute to a deeper understanding of how changes in classroom lighting contribute to the visual perception and cognitive performance of occupants.

According to Yang et al (2020), the parameters affected by lighting in a classroom include the optimal visibility of all information to the students, the mood or behaviour of the students, and the learning ability and performance of students. The study's examined the impact of Correlated Color Temperature (CCT) of LED light on visual sensation, perception, and cognitive performance within a classroom lighting environment. The findings revealed that men exhibited CCT effects on working memory spaces, whereas women's working memory spaces remained unaffected by both CCT and illuminance. Nevertheless, this study necessitates further exploration into the enduring effects of CCT on lighting perception relative to various levels of brain processing and comprehensive cognitive performance. Enhanced precision in measurements at the human eye level is imperative for a more thorough understanding. This study has provided valuable insights into the influence of specific CCT levels and illuminance on students' cognitive performance. Moreover, it has facilitated a nuanced comprehension of gender-related disparities in glare sensation and working memory test outcomes. Notably, women

demonstrated heightened sensitivity to glare sensation and achieved lower mean scores in the working memory test compared to their male counterparts.

Findings from the research conducted by Tureková et al. (2018) have substantiated that the quality of the school environment significantly impacts students' academic performance. Accurate lighting is a crucial factor influencing the work environment, playing a vital role in visual tasks and consequently affecting either visual comfort or visual fatigue. This study presents the outcomes of the lighting objectification of a selected university classroom, with a specific focus on detecting the daylight factor—an essential criterion for assessing the amount of daylight in the classroom. The value of the daylight factor is a relative magnitude dependent on the correct spatial layout of the classroom. The results of the study indicate insufficient values of this indicator. In conclusion, a software solution is proposed for replacing the artificial lighting in the classroom, representing a potential alternative to enhance the visual comfort of the learning space.

Visual comfort, defined as "a subjective condition of visual well-being induced by the visual environment", exerts a decisive influence on occupants' performance, mood, and overall functionality. In this context, researchers have directed their focus toward aspects such as students' health, well-being, learning, and visual performance (Korsavi et al., 2016). Some studies have underscored the correlation between insufficient illuminance levels and disruptions in human rhythms, safety concerns, and potential health implications. Key visual comfort indices, prove instrumental in optimizing the integrated design of buildings, leading to potential energy savings (Carlucci et al., 2015)¹⁷. Numerous research endeavours have been undertaken to optimize lighting performance, aiming to minimize artificial lighting's energy consumption within interior environments.

The study of lighting in educational spaces has evolved over the years, addressing a spectrum of themes that contribute to a nuanced understanding of this essential aspect. Research in this domain has explored diverse topics, ranging from energy efficiency to considerations of performance, mood, cognition, perception, and visual comfort. The choice of focus within these themes often aligns with evolving research interests and prevailing trends, reflective of scientific developments and technological advancements characteristic of each era.

The evolution of research methods and tools represents both a response to contemporary challenges and a driver of advancements in the field. In the context of this review, particular attention is directed towards understanding how past studies measured outcomes within their respective areas of investigation and correlated these outcomes with specific lighting characteristics.

The deliberate emphasis of visual comfort is through aligning with the recognition of its profound impact on occupants' well-being and performance. This reinforces the importance of comprehensively understanding and optimizing illuminance quality in educational environments, forming a significant rationale for the focus on visual comfort in the present research endeavour.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

The lighting environment within an educational setting plays a pivotal role in shaping students' overall well-being and academic achievement. Despite the acknowledged importance of sufficient lighting, there exists a gap in comprehensive analyses tailored to university buildings, encompassing both artificial and natural lighting.

The primary objective of this study is to assess illuminance quality in four selected classrooms within the Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus New Building, College of Engineering with a focus on enhancing visual comfort.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the profiles of each classroom in terms of:
 - 1.1. Classroom Dimension
 - 1.2. Seat Capacity
 - 1.3. Window Characteristics and orientation
 - 1.4. Door Orientation
 - 1.5. Classroom fixtures, wall properties, and equipment
2. What is the mean score of each selected classroom in regards to the following parameters that influence visual comfort?
 - 2.1. Illuminance Level
 - 2.2. Illuminance Uniformity
 - 2.3. Wall Surface Reflectance

3. What are the descriptive empirical comparisons for each classroom, based on scheduled time, in relation to the set standards for each parameter regarding:
 - 3.1. Cumulative Distribution Frequency
 - 3.2. Mean Position
4. Is there a significant difference among the selected classrooms based on the mean scores obtained for each of the aforementioned parameters?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations for improvement may be proposed?

Significance of the Study

The outcomes of this study will be valuable to the following:

Students. Students are the most affected by the lighting quality in university buildings since they spend most of their time indoors. The students can highly profit from this research since it may lead to improvements in their learning environment, positively influencing their visual comfort, concentration, and overall satisfaction. Students will benefit from a more conducive atmosphere for academic success.

Faculty and Staff. As the prime advocates for academic engagement, they play a pivotal role in creating innovative strategies and fostering collaborative learning environments. This study would be an epiphany for the industrial engineering department and intensify the educators' efficacy in ensuring students' visual comfort and overall well-being. This knowledge can inform decision-making related to lighting design, technology

interventions, and facility management practices, fostering a more supportive environment for both teaching and work.

School Administrator. As a leader of the school, they would be able to spearhead comprehensive initiatives to improve the lighting conditions across the university buildings. The findings may be used to recognize the current status of lighting conditions in alleviating the gaps in creating a conducive learning environment. The institution stands to benefit from enhanced well-being and satisfaction among its students and staff, contributing to a positive campus culture.

Researchers. Strategies undergo adaptation in response to emerging eras. This study would be a credible reference for supplementary analysis. The findings of this research will pave the way for subsequent investigations, leading to the formulation of more practical measures for enhancing the university's structural framework. Furthermore, researchers can discern pertinent insights from this strategy, proving valuable in comparing methodological timelines for future applications and advancing studies on lighting conditions and their influence on occupants.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method

An integrated research methodology, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative approaches, was proposed to analyze illuminance quality in the new Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus building, with a central focus on enhancing visual comfort. The objective was to identify standard classrooms and those requiring further improvement.

In particular, the qualitative approach was employed to determine classroom specifications, while light meters were used to take objective measurements of illuminance levels and other relevant parameters influencing visual comfort.

Flow of the Study

Research Environment

This research endeavor was conducted within the premises of Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus (9.9416° N, 123.3944° E), situated in Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu, Philippines. The focus of the study was the recently constructed university building, a four-story educational facility. The ground floor was designated for administrative offices, while the subsequent three floors (2nd, 3rd, and 4th storeys) served as instructional spaces, each comprising four classrooms. Of particular significance to this research was the assessment of four classrooms on the 4th floor (IE ROOM 1, IE ROOM 2, IE ROOM 3, and IE ROOM 5), with a specific emphasis on classrooms under the College of Engineering.

Figure 2. Location Map of the Study

Figure 3. Positions of Rooms in CTU Moalboal Campus New Building

Figure 4. Classroom Site Layout

Instruments

The primary instrument for this research was lux meters designed to accurately measure illuminance levels. A total of 6 digital lux meter (Intelli Sensor, Smart Sensor, AS803) was used to measure the illuminance levels in the classrooms. This device was strategically deployed exclusively in four classrooms. The focused approach involved systematic measurements across various classroom settings to assess illumination quality.

Figure 5. Lux meter

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure primarily involved illumination measurements. To begin, the researcher sought permission from the department dean through a transmittal letter outlining the purpose and scope of the study.

Illuminance measurements were taken at various locations within the university building, particularly in the four classrooms on the 4th floor, using light meters to cover both natural and artificial lighting conditions. The researchers measured the illuminance level, illuminance uniformity, and wall surface reflection inside the classrooms without any intervention at different times of the day.

Assessment of Classroom Illuminance Level

Illuminance is a measure of how much incident light falls on a surface and is expressed in lux, representing the total luminous flux per unit area (lumens per m²).

Illuminance measurements were systematically conducted four times a day—at 7:30 AM, 10:00 AM, 12:30 PM, and 3:00 PM. The classroom was divided into a 2 x 3 grid, enabling structured collection of illuminance data across each section.

Figure 6. Classroom Layout Divided Into a 2x3 Grid

Six lux meters were deployed, each positioned in a different grid, ensuring simultaneous measurements. Measurements were taken at desk height, where tasks are typically performed. The sampling equipment was set up with the sensor facing upward and perpendicular to the light source, and allowed to stabilize before recording illuminance levels in lux. Both minimum and average illuminance measurements were documented for each grid point. These procedures were carried out, with all artificial lights turned on. Only researchers were present during readings, ensuring that no obstructions existed between the light source and measurement points. Multiple readings were gathered to ensure accuracy of the data.

Assessment of Classroom Illuminance Uniformity

Illuminance Uniformity (U_0) of a given plane is defined as the ratio, in a given moment, between the minimum value of the illuminance on the plane (E_{\min}) and the average illuminance on that plane (E_{average}).

$$U_0 = \frac{E_{\min}}{E_{\text{average}}}$$

U_0 is a short-term and zonal index assessing the uniformity of light.

For the measurement of illuminance uniformity, the classroom was divided into a 2 x 3 grid. At each grid point, illuminance was measured using a lux meter. Subsequently, the ratio between the minimum and average illuminance values was calculated to evaluate uniformity. A higher uniformity ratio indicated better uniformity, thereby enhancing comfort for occupants.

Assessment of Classroom Surface Reflectance

Surface reflectance is the ratio of luminous flux reflected by a body (with or without diffusion) to the flux it receives (Chandel et al., 2015)

In typical lighting design research, surface reflectance is commonly assessed using a luminance meter. However, due to cost constraints, an alternative method will be utilized in this study. An alternative approach for measuring reflectance is proposed by Jupp (1997) and Mousavi et al. (2018), where reflectance is determined by the ratio of reflected to incident illuminance:

$$\rho = \frac{E_r}{E_i}$$

where:

E_r is the reflected illuminance in lux

E_i is the incident illuminance in lux

ρ is the reflectance of the surface

The measurement process involved multiple repetitions for the selected surfaces (walls), including the front wall where the board was located, both side walls, and the rear wall. To measure the incident illuminance, the sampling equipment was positioned at an appropriate distance from the wall surface, ensuring it was perpendicular to the wall and facing the light source. For the reflected illuminance measurement, the equipment was also placed at an appropriate distance from the wall surface, with the setup remaining perpendicular to the wall and facing directly toward it. The measurement of wall surface reflectance noted that the distance of the lux meter sensors from all the studied surfaces was approximately 2.3 ft under all conditions (Mousavi et al., 2018).

Statistical Treatment

To interpret the gathered data, the researcher utilized several statistical techniques. For the illuminance conditions in the new university building, descriptive statistics, such as mean illuminance levels and standard deviations, were employed to provide a summary. A Bell Curve (Normal Distribution) was also used to align the collected data with established lighting standards. By analyzing the data distribution

through the bell curve, the researcher assessed how closely the measured values conformed to the expected standard range, identifying areas that required improvement or adjustments. Furthermore, the study employed a One-Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) and Tukey HSD test to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the means of illuminance level, illuminance uniformity, and surface reflectance for each classroom. The Tukey HSD test served as a post-hoc analysis to pinpoint which of the four classrooms exhibited significant differences. These tests provided pairwise comparisons, revealing discrepancies among the three parameters (illuminance level, uniformity, and wall surface reflectance) of each classroom.

Definition of Terms

Adequate Lighting. It refers to having enough good lighting in a particular area or setting to meet the visual needs.

Artificial light. Light produced by human-made sources, primarily the sun, providing illumination that changes based on time and weather.

Cumulative Distribution Frequency. A statistical measure that shows the cumulative proportion or count of values up to a certain point, representing the probability that a random variable takes a value less than or equal to that point.

Natural Light. Light that comes from natural sources, such as bulbs or LEDs, used to illuminate spaces in the absence or supplementation of natural light.

Illuminance. It refers to the measurement of how much light illuminates a given surface area, measured in lux.

Incident illuminance. It refers to the light that falls on an object or a surface from different directions, creating a shadow, and patterns of shading that impacts its appearance.

Lighting. It denotes the intentional use of artificial or natural light sources to achieve practical or aesthetic effects in a given space

Luminance. The intensity of light emitted or reflected from a surface in a particular direction, perceived as brightness, measured in candela per square meter (cd/m^2).

Reflected Illuminance. The light that bounces off surfaces, contributing to the overall lighting level in a space and affecting its brightness.

Surface Reflectance. The ratio of luminous flux reflected by a body (with or without diffusion) to the flux it receives.

Task Plane. The specific surface are where tasks are performed, such as desks or countertop, requiring adequate lighting for visual clarity.

Uniformity. The consistency or evenness of a quality, or distribution across a given area.

Visual Comfort. The degree of satisfaction to which lighting conditions enable clear vision without causing eye strain, glare, or discomfort.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION, DATA, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of raw data related to the problems stated in the SOP. The corresponding analysis and interpretation of data are based on the study of illuminance level, illuminance uniformity, and wall surface reflectance in the selected classrooms from the College of Engineering Department at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus.

CLASSROOM SPECIFICATIONS

Table 4. Classroom Specifications of Assessed Classroom

Classroom			Window Characteristics	Window Orientation	Door Orientation
No.	Dimension (LxWxH)	Seat Capacity			
1	7.83x 7.1 x 2.72	40	Front: Sliding glass windows	Front windows facing west; rear windows facing northeast.	Two doors in each classroom, both on the front side and facing west.
2	7.83x 7.1 x 2.72	50	Rear: Tinted jalousie windows with fixed glass in the upper part.		
3	7.83x 7.1 x 2.72	50			
5	7.83x 7.1 x 2.72	40			

The classroom assessment was conducted in rooms situated on the fourth floor of a newly constructed building – College of Engineering Department at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus. These rooms were enclosed and featured sliding windows and jalousie windows fitted with curtains with minimal sunlight managed to filter through. The assessment took place in the month of March, coinciding with a period of favorable (sunny) weather conditions in the Philippines.

Characteristics of Assessed Classrooms

Figure 7. Room 1 Layout

Figure 8. Room 1 Actual Set Up

Figures 7 and 8 depict the actual layout and setup of **Room 1** during the assessment. The room's walls are painted white. It contains various types of furniture, including two glass boards on the front wall, 40 student armchairs arranged on the left side, and two additional armchairs on the right side. Three cabinets of varying sizes are positioned along the back wall. There are also two monitors: one is a television on a table

at the front, and the other is a computer on a separate table to the right. A jalousie window with white curtains is present. The layout remained unchanged throughout the data collection process.

Figure 9. Room 2 Layout

Figure 10. Room 2 Actual Set Up

Figures 9 and 10 shows the actual picture and layout of **Room 2** during the assessment. The room's walls are painted white, and a jalousie window is covered with white curtains. Room 2 features two glass boards placed against the front wall, 50 student

armchairs arranged in the center, and three drafting tables of the same size positioned next to each other on the left side. At the front of the room, there is one table with a television placed on top, along with another table at the center-front that includes an extra chair. Additionally, two cabinets of the same size are situated in the corner on the right side of the room. The layout remained unchanged throughout the data-gathering process.

Figure 11. Room 3 Layout

Figure 12. Room 3 Actual Set Up

Figures 11 and 12 show the actual layout and setup of **Room 3** during the assessment. The room features white walls and light pink curtains. It contains two glass boards on the front wall and 50 student armchairs, with 25 placed in the center and the other 25 on the left side. A small partition is located in the front-right corner, with a table placed against it that holds a computer. Additionally, there is a table on the right side of the room with four computers, each featuring a mirrored side on the system unit, along with two extra armchairs in the right corner. The television is mounted on the upper front wall of the room.

Figure 13. Room 5 Layout

Figure 14. Room 5 Actual Set Up

Figures 13 and 14 depict the actual picture and layout of **Room 5** during the assessment. The room's walls are painted white, and the windows are covered with light pink curtains. The room contains two glass boards placed against the front wall. A small partition is positioned in the right corner, with a table placed against it that holds three computers. Another table is positioned at the front right corner, topped with a television, while an additional table is along the right side wall, and one more table is located at the front center. Additionally, two extra armchairs are situated in the right corner of the room. The layout remained consistent throughout the data collection process.

ASSESSMENT OF ILLUMINANCE LEVEL, UNIFORMITY, AND WALL SURFACE REFLECTANCE IN SELECTED CLASSROOMS

This section presents the key findings from the analysis, focusing on the trends and patterns observed in illuminance level, uniformity, and wall surface reflectance across the selected classrooms.

Assessment of Classroom Illuminance Level

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Room 1 Illuminance Level

Time Period	AVERAGE ILLUMINANCE LEVEL (lux)						Mean	SD
	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	Point 4	Point 5	Point 6		
7:30 - 10:00	340.27	309.60	378.53	341.00	525.33	311.67	367.73	74.10
10:00 - 12:30	330.67	354.47	427.67	359.00	390.47	345.93	368.03	32.17
12:30 -15:00	270.87	328.00	305.53	352.87	296.53	289.27	307.18	26.70
15:00 - 17:30	275.33	332.67	268.07	323.20	289.60	310.93	299.97	24.02
Mean	304.28	331.18	344.95	344.02	375.48	314.45	335.73	

In Room 1, Table 5 shows the average mean results from the summation of the illuminance levels at Points 1 to 6 across different time intervals. From 7:30 to 10:00 AM, the average mean was 367.73 lux, with a corresponding standard deviation (SD) of 74.10. This was followed by an average mean of 368.03 lux and an SD of 32.17 from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM. In the third time category, from 12:30 to 15:00 PM, the average mean was 307.18 lux, with an SD of 26.70. For the last time category, from 15:00 to 17:00 PM, the average mean was 299.97 lux, with a corresponding SD of 24.02. Thus, the average

illuminance level mean obtained from the summation of all the means from Points 1 to 6 was 335.73 lux.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Room 2 Illuminance Level

Time Period	AVERAGE ILLUMINANCE LEVEL (lux)						Mean	SD
	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	Point 4	Point 5	Point 6		
7:30 - 10:00	1705.73	405.60	1589.00	380.33	534.33	388.27	833.88	578.47
10:00 - 12:30	543.13	404.40	352.13	342.20	414.27	361.13	402.88	68.07
12:30 - 15:00	402.40	385.73	335.93	324.40	293.80	330.27	345.42	37.19
15:00 - 17:30	394.07	416.47	341.47	409.00	310.20	348.93	370.02	38.93
Mean	761.33	403.05	654.63	363.98	388.15	357.15	488.05	

The results presented in Table 6 for the illuminance level of Room 2 show an average mean of 833.88 lux for the time category from 7:30 to 10:00 AM, with a standard deviation (SD) of 578.47. Subsequently, from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the average mean was 402.88 lux, with an SD of 68.07. In the next time category, from 12:30 to 15:00 PM, the average mean was 345.42 lux, with an SD of 37.19. Lastly, from 15:00 to 17:30 PM, the average mean was 370.02 lux, with a corresponding SD of 38.93. Overall, the average illuminance level mean was 488.05 lux.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of Room 3 Illuminance Level

Time Period	AVERAGE ILLUMINANCE LEVEL (lux)						Mean	SD
	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	Point 4	Point 5	Point 6		
7:30 - 10:00	367.27	366.20	485.33	397.53	492.00	335.80	407.36	60.23
10:00 - 12:30	333.47	391.60	462.60	389.00	401.20	325.87	383.96	45.62
12:30 -15:00	293.67	365.13	336.27	373.07	410.00	396.13	362.38	38.58
15:00 - 17:30	253.93	266.53	349.80	298.00	280.53	281.93	288.46	30.64
Mean	312.08	347.37	408.50	364.40	395.93	334.93	360.54	

The data shown in Table 7 for the illuminance level in Room 3 indicate that the average illuminance from 7:30 to 10:00 AM was 407.36 lux, with a standard deviation (SD) of 60.23. In the following time period, from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the average decreased to 383.96 lux, accompanied by an SD of 45.62. During the next interval, from 12:30 to 15:00 PM, the average further dropped to 362.38 lux, with an SD of 38.58. Finally, from 15:00 to 17:30 PM, the average was 288.46 lux, with an SD of 30.64. Overall, the average illuminance level across all time periods was 360.54 lux.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics of Room 5 Illuminance Level

Time Period	AVERAGE ILLUMINANCE LEVEL (lux)						Mean	SD
	Point 1	Point 2	Point 3	Point 4	Point 5	Point 6		
7:30 - 10:00	600.80	486.93	409.40	432.80	371.47	434.07	455.91	73.33
10:00 - 12:30	438.93	452.13	406.07	354.60	361.00	363.33	396.01	38.95
12:30 -15:00	408.87	430.20	408.47	344.13	323.80	394.80	385.04	38.02
15:00 - 17:30	362.33	375.27	319.87	341.33	316.67	366.07	346.92	22.68
Mean	452.73	436.13	385.95	368.22	343.23	389.57	395.97	

Table 8 presents the average illuminance levels for Points 1 through 6 at various time intervals in Room 5. The mean illuminance for the period from 7:30 to 10:00 AM was 455.91 lux, with a standard deviation (SD) of 73.33. From 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the mean decreased to 396.01 lux, accompanied by an SD of 38.95. In the third time period, from 12:30 to 15:00 PM, the average was 385.04 lux, with an SD of 38.02. Finally, from 15:00 to 17:30 PM, the mean was 346.92 lux, with a standard deviation of 22.68. Consequently, when all means from Points 1 to 6 were summed, the overall average illuminance level was 395.97 lux.

Assessment of Classroom Illuminance Uniformity

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics of Room 1 Illuminance Uniformity

Time Period	Average Illuminance Level (lux)			ILLUMINANCE UNIFORMITY	SD
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		
7:30 - 10:00	260.40	538.67	367.73	0.70	0.11
10:00 - 12:30	286.27	456.87	368.03	0.78	0.07
12:30 -15:00	244.00	373.53	307.18	0.79	0.09
15:00 - 17:30	208.33	374.33	299.97	0.69	0.12
Mean			335.73	0.74	

The illuminance uniformity in Room 1, with an overall mean of 0.74, indicates fairly consistent lighting throughout the day, though there are some fluctuations (Table 9). The period from 10:00 to 12:30 shows the highest uniformity at 0.78 (SD = 0.07), with minimal variation, while the afternoon period from 12:30 to 15:00 also maintains good uniformity at 0.79 (SD = 0.09). However, during the early morning (7:30 to 10:00) and late afternoon (15:00 to 17:30), the uniformity drops to 0.70 and 0.69, respectively, with higher standard deviations of 0.11 and 0.12, indicating more variability in lighting during these times. Overall, the room maintains a reasonable level of light distribution, but consistency is lower at the start and end of the day.

Table 10. Descriptive Statistics of Room 2 Illuminance Uniformity

Time Period	Average Illuminance Level (lux)			ILLUMINANCE UNIFORMITY	SD
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		
7:30 - 10:00	347.40	2102.13	833.88	0.57	0.21
10:00 - 12:30	257.20	554.27	402.88	0.64	0.20
12:30 -15:00	249.33	431.00	345.42	0.71	0.14
15:00 - 17:30	263.93	465.53	370.02	0.70	0.14
Mean			488.05	0.65	

The illuminance uniformity values for Room 2 across different time periods exhibit varying degrees of consistency (Table 10). During the period from 7:30 to 10:00, the uniformity was measured at 0.57 with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.21, indicating relatively low uniformity. This improved slightly during the 10:00 to 12:30 period, where the uniformity reached 0.64 and the SD was 0.20. The highest level of uniformity was recorded from 12:30 to 15:00 at 0.71, accompanied by a lower SD of 0.14, suggesting more consistent lighting conditions. In the final period from 15:00 to 17:30, the uniformity remained high at 0.70 with the same SD of 0.14. Overall, the average illuminance uniformity for the room was calculated at 0.65, indicating a moderately uniform lighting environment.

Table 11. Descriptive Statistics of Room 3 Illuminance Uniformity

Time Period	Average Illuminance Level (lux)			ILLUMINANCE UNIFORMITY	SD
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		
7:30 - 10:00	288.40	581.73	407.36	0.71	0.07
10:00 - 12:30	292.47	485.33	383.96	0.76	0.05
12:30 -15:00	277.60	451.40	362.38	0.76	0.13
15:00 - 17:30	208.87	373.40	288.46	0.72	0.09
Mean			360.54	0.74	

The illuminance uniformity data for Room 3 reveals varying levels of uniformity across different time periods, as shown in Table 11. During the first period (7:30 - 10:00), the illuminance uniformity value was 0.71 with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.07, indicating a moderate level of consistency in light distribution. This slightly improved during the next interval (10:00 - 12:30), where the uniformity value reached 0.76, accompanied by a lower SD of 0.05, suggesting a more uniform light distribution. The trend continued with a consistent uniformity value of 0.76 and a higher SD of 0.13 in the period from 12:30 to 15:00. However, from 15:00 to 17:30, the uniformity dropped to 0.72 with an SD of 0.09, indicating some reduction in uniformity. Overall, the average illuminance uniformity for the room was 0.74, suggesting a generally acceptable level of light distribution, though there are fluctuations that could impact visual comfort and functionality in the space.

Table 12. Descriptive Statistics of Room 5 Illuminance Uniformity

Time Period	Average Illuminance Level (lux)			ILLUMINANCE UNIFORMITY	SD
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		
7:30 - 10:00	331.73	635.60	455.91	0.73	0.11
10:00 - 12:30	291.53	478.07	396.01	0.73	0.11
12:30 -15:00	283.53	486.20	385.04	0.73	0.05
15:00 - 17:30	255.53	435.73	346.92	0.73	0.14
Mean			395.97	0.73	

The illuminance uniformity values for Room 5 varied across different time periods, with a consistent mean of 0.73, indicating stable uniformity throughout the day (Table 12). During the period from 7:30 to 10:00, the standard deviation (SD) was 0.11, reflecting minor variability in uniformity. The following time period, from 10:00 to 12:30, maintained the same mean uniformity of 0.73 with an SD of 0.11, suggesting similar consistency. In the 12:30 to 15:00 period, while the mean remained unchanged at 0.73, the SD decreased to 0.05, indicating improved uniformity. Lastly, from 15:00 to 17:30, the mean uniformity again was 0.73, but the SD rose to 0.14, suggesting a slight increase in variability. Overall, the illuminance uniformity for the room remains steady with an average SD of 0.11, highlighting a reliable lighting condition throughout the observed periods.

Assessment of Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance

Table 13. Descriptive Statistics of Room 1 Wall Surface Reflectance

Wall Surface Reflectance						
Time	Front			Right		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	243.27	156.00	0.64	182.00	168.80	0.93
10:00 - 12:30	163.53	106.87	0.65	162.60	95.47	0.59
12:30 - 15:00	171.20	133.33	0.78	175.67	73.47	0.42
15:00 - 17:30	196.53	136.60	0.70	202.80	81.93	0.40
Mean	193.63	133.20	0.69	180.77	104.92	0.58

Time	Left			Rear		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	136.47	91.67	0.67	176.13	113.93	0.65
10:00 - 12:30	112.47	83.87	0.75	154.93	111.00	0.72
12:30 - 15:00	121.53	116.27	0.96	159.00	130.73	0.82
15:00 - 17:30	122.33	105.60	0.86	166.47	110.87	0.67
Mean	123.20	99.35	0.81	164.13	116.63	0.71

	Front Wall	Right Wall	Left Wall	Rear Wall	Mean	SD
7:30 - 10:00	0.64	0.93	0.67	0.65	0.72	0.12
10:00 - 12:30	0.65	0.59	0.75	0.72	0.68	0.06
12:30 - 15:00	0.78	0.42	0.96	0.82	0.74	0.20
15:00 - 17:30	0.70	0.40	0.86	0.67	0.66	0.16
Mean	0.69	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.70	

The data shown in Table 13 indicates that in Room 1, wall surface reflectance in front wall has an average reflectance of 0.69, while the right wall averages 0.58, with a

peak of 0.93 in the morning. The left wall shows an average reflectance of 0.81, and the rear wall averages 0.71. In the morning (7:30 - 10:00), the average wall surface reflectance is 0.72, with a standard deviation of 0.12, indicating a reliable level of light distribution across the walls. This average decreases slightly to 0.68 (SD = 0.06) between 10:00 and 12:30, suggesting a minor reduction in overall surface efficiency as daylight increases. In the afternoon (12:30 - 15:00), the reflectance rises to 0.74, accompanied by a higher standard deviation of 0.20, indicating increased variability in wall performance during this period. However, reflectance drops to 0.66 (SD = 0.16) later in the day (15:00 - 17:30), highlighting a decline in surface reflectance effectiveness as natural light diminishes. The overall mean surface reflectance of Room 1 across all time periods is 0.70, reflecting a moderate ability of the walls to enhance illumination throughout the day.

Table 14. Descriptive Statistics of Room 2 Wall Surface Reflectance

Wall Surface Reflectance						
Time	Front			Right		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	251.40	151.87	0.60	142.84	212.40	1.49
10:00 - 12:30	260.80	162.27	0.62	224.53	160.27	0.71
12:30 - 15:00	226.80	133.53	0.59	209.53	165.33	0.79
15:00 - 17:30	241.87	143.73	0.59	244.80	150.27	0.61
Mean	245.22	147.85	0.60	205.43	172.07	0.90

Time	Left			Rear		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	163.07	140.27	0.86	233.80	167.47	0.72
10:00 - 12:30	170.07	150.53	0.89	224.53	160.27	0.71
12:30 - 15:00	151.60	132.87	0.88	212.20	178.80	0.84
15:00 - 17:30	148.07	128.93	0.87	173.13	159.93	0.92
Mean	158.20	138.15	0.87	210.92	166.62	0.80

	Front Wall	Right Wall	Left Wall	Rear Wall	Mean	SD
7:30 - 10:00	0.60	1.49	0.86	0.72	0.92	0.34
10:00 - 12:30	0.62	0.71	0.89	0.71	0.73	0.10
12:30 - 15:00	0.59	0.79	0.88	0.84	0.78	0.11
15:00 - 17:30	0.59	0.61	0.87	0.92	0.75	0.15
Mean	0.60	0.90	0.87	0.80	0.79	

The wall surface reflectance in Room 2 varies across different walls, as shown in the Table 14. The front wall has an average reflectance of 0.60, while the right wall, averages 0.90. The left wall shows a consistent average reflectance of 0.87, and the rear

wall has an average of 0.80. During the time period from 7:30 to 10:00, the average wall surface reflectance across all walls is 0.92, with a high standard deviation of 0.34, indicating significant variability in reflectance among the walls. This average reflectance decreases to 0.73 (SD = 0.10) between 10:00 and 12:30, suggesting improved consistency in wall performance as the day progresses. In the afternoon (12:30 - 15:00), reflectance rises slightly to 0.78 (SD = 0.11), demonstrating a steady light distribution across the walls. However, there is a subsequent decline to 0.75 (SD = 0.15) in the late afternoon (15:00 - 17:30), reflecting a reduction in overall wall effectiveness as natural light decreases. The overall mean surface reflectance of Room 2 across all time periods is 0.79.

Table 15. Descriptive Statistics of Room 3 Wall Surface Reflectance

Wall Surface Reflectance						
Time	Front			Right		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	270.13	144.87	0.54	261.80	557.53	2.13
10:00 - 12:30	214.87	134.27	0.62	169.67	206.07	1.21
12:30 - 15:00	281.53	132.13	0.47	196.20	244.60	1.25
15:00 - 17:30	210.87	122.20	0.58	174.00	205.13	1.18
Mean	244.35	133.37	0.55	200.42	303.33	1.44

Time	Left			Rear		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	182.87	138.07	0.76	231.80	174.33	0.75
10:00 - 12:30	162.67	142.60	0.88	239.67	177.67	0.74
12:30 - 15:00	135.47	103.00	0.76	188.53	156.87	0.83
15:00 - 17:30	127.40	170.67	1.34	167.60	133.53	0.80
Mean	152.10	138.58	0.93	206.90	160.60	0.78

	Front Wall	Right Wall	Left Wall	Rear Wall	Mean	SD
7:30 - 10:00	0.54	2.13	0.76	0.75	1.05	0.63
10:00 - 12:30	0.62	1.21	0.88	0.74	0.86	0.22
12:30 - 15:00	0.47	1.25	0.76	0.83	0.83	0.28
15:00 - 17:30	0.58	1.18	1.34	0.80	0.98	0.30
Mean					0.93	

In Room 3, as shown in Table 15, the front wall surface reflectance averages 0.55, while the rear wall is higher at 0.78. The right wall shows a notable average reflectance of 1.44, especially in the morning. The left wall averages 0.93. The average wall surface

reflectance across all walls in Room 3 is 1.05 from 7:30 to 10:00, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.63, indicating substantial variability in light distribution during this period. Subsequently, the average reflectance decreases to 0.86 (SD = 0.22) between 10:00 and 12:30, suggesting a reduction in light levels. In the afternoon (12:30 to 15:00), the reflectance decreases slightly further to 0.83 (SD = 0.28), indicating a continued decline in illumination. However, there is an increase in reflectance to 0.98 (SD = 0.30) during the late afternoon (15:00 to 17:30), reflecting improved light interaction with the walls. Overall, the mean surface reflectance across all time periods in Room 3 is 0.93, suggesting a moderate efficiency in reflecting light, which may influence the overall lighting conditions in the room.

Table 16. Descriptive Statistics of Room 5 Wall Surface Reflectance

Wall Surface Reflectance						
Time	Front			Right		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	220.33	122.00	0.55	177.27	227.80	1.29
10:00 - 12:30	204.60	141.80	0.69	141.80	129.80	0.92
12:30 - 15:00	218.47	127.60	0.58	158.40	96.73	0.61
15:00 - 17:30	205.47	134.67	0.66	155.07	107.33	0.69
Mean	212.22	131.52	0.62	158.13	140.42	0.88

Time	Left			Rear		
	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance	Illuminance		Surface Reflectance
	Incident	Reflected		Incident	Reflected	
7:30 - 10:00	145.07	172.60	1.19	189.07	145.47	0.77
10:00 - 12:30	136.67	129.53	0.95	161.33	100.13	0.62
12:30 - 15:00	147.33	178.13	1.21	187.67	127.53	0.68
15:00 - 17:30	127.40	170.67	1.34	167.60	133.53	0.80
Mean	139.12	162.73	1.17	176.42	126.67	0.72

	Front Wall	Right Wall	Left Wall	Rear Wall	Mean	SD
7:30 - 10:00	0.55	1.29	1.19	0.77	0.95	0.30
10:00 - 12:30	0.69	0.92	0.95	0.62	0.80	0.14
12:30 - 15:00	0.58	0.61	1.21	0.68	0.77	0.26
15:00 - 17:30	0.66	0.69	1.34	0.80	0.87	0.27
Mean					0.85	

Table 16 presents the wall surface reflectance measurements for Room 5, the front wall averages a reflectance of 0.62, while the back wall averages 0.72. The right wall has a higher average reflectance of 0.88, and the left wall stands out with an average of 1.17.

The wall surface reflectance measurements for Room 5 indicate that the average reflectance across all walls is 0.95 from 7:30 to 10:00, with a standard deviation of 0.30, suggesting considerable variability in light distribution. This average decreases to 0.80 (SD = 0.14) between 10:00 and 12:30. In the afternoon (12:30 to 15:00), the reflectance declines further to 0.77 (SD = 0.26). However, there is an increase in reflectance to 0.87 (SD = 0.27) during the late afternoon (15:00 to 17:30). Overall, the mean surface reflectance across all time periods in Room 5 is 0.85, reflecting a moderate level of light reflectance that may influence the overall lighting conditions within the space.

ASSESSMENT OF CLASSROOM COMPLIANCE WITH ESTABLISHED STANDARDS

This section focuses on evaluating classroom compliance with established standards to determine whether classrooms meet the necessary criteria for fostering a conducive learning environment for both students and educators.

Table 17. *Parameters for Visual Comfort Standards*

STANDARDS		
Illuminance Level	GRIHA V – 2015:	300 – 500 lux
Illuminance Uniformity	ISO/CIE 8995	$U_{O, min} = 0.7$
Wall Surface Reflectance	CIBSE Code for Lighting: Walls	0.5-0.8

Table 17 presents one of the essential parameters for visual comfort. It recommends illuminance levels of 300 to 500 lux according to GRIHA V – 2015 (Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment), ensuring adequate visibility. It also sets a minimum illuminance uniformity ratio of 0.7, per ISO/CIE 8995 (International Organization for Standardization/International Electrotechnical Commission), to promote even light distribution. Additionally, it specifies a wall surface reflectance range of 0.5 to 0.8, based on CIBSE (Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers) guidelines, to enhance lighting efficiency and comfort.

Classroom Illuminance Level Compliance

Figure 15. Classroom Illuminance Level: 7:30 AM – 10:00 AM

Figure 15 illustrates the illuminance levels of four rooms from 7:30 to 10:00, compared with the GRIHA 2015 standard range of 300 to 500 lux. Room 1 has a mean illuminance of 367.73 lux and a standard deviation (SD) of 74.10 with a corresponding cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 78%, indicating that 78% of the measurements fall below average value. This suggests that while the room meets the standard, there are periods when the lighting may dip closer to the lower limit of 300 lux, which could affect visual comfort. Room 2 shows a mean illuminance of 833.88 lux, an SD of 578.47, and a CDF of 10%, means that 90% of the measurements exceed this average significantly, indicating severe over-illumination. This level of lighting is likely to cause discomfort, call for adjustments such as dimming to bring it within the acceptable range. In contrast, Room 3 has a mean illuminance of 407.36 lux, a 60.23 SD, and a CDF of 90%, indicating that

90% of the measurements are below the average value, reflecting stable lighting that aligns well with the recommended standards. Lastly, Room 5 has a mean illuminance of 455.91 lux with 73.33 SD and a CDF of 71%, suggesting that while the room provides adequate lighting, 71% of the measurements still fall below the average value. The figure highlights that while Rooms 1, 3, and 5 provide adequate lighting, adjustments are essential in Room 2 to reduce over-illumination, and attention should be given to Rooms 1 and 5 to enhance consistency and ensure a comfortable lighting environment. According to Singh and Arora (2014), providing adequate illumination in the classroom can increase student's concentration leading to a more improved performance.

Figure 16. Classroom Illuminance Level: 10:00 AM – 12:30 PM

Figure 16 illustrates the illuminance levels of four rooms from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, as compared to the 300-500 lux GRIHA 2015 standard range. Room 1 has a mean illuminance of 368.03 lux, a 32.17 SD, and a CDF of 98%, this means that 98% of the

measurements falls below average value, suggesting that the lighting approaches the lower limit of 300 lux at times. Room 2 shows a mean illuminance of 402.88 lux and an SD of 68.07 with its CDF of 86%, which means 86% of the measurements are below the average level, reflecting generally suitable lighting with some fluctuations. In contrast, Room 3 has a mean illuminance of 383.96 lux, SD of 45.62, and a CDF of 96%, indicating that 96% of the measurements are below the average value, providing a stable environment for visual comfort. Lastly, Room 5 has a mean illuminance of 396.01 lux and an SD of 38.95 together with a CDF of 99%, suggesting that the lighting is consistent and meets the average value for nearly the entire observation period. The figure highlights that while Rooms 1, 3, and 5 provide adequate lighting, adjustments in Room 1 could enhance consistency, and Room 2 may benefit from further stabilization to prevent dips below the lower limit of 300 lux.

Figure 17. Classroom Illuminance Level: 12:30 PM – 15:00 PM

Figure 17 presents the illuminance levels of four rooms from 12:30 PM to 15:00 PM, measured against the GRIHA 2015 standard range of 300 to 500 lux. Room 1 has a mean illuminance of 307.18 lux and an SD of 26.70 with a CDF of 61%, indicating that 61% of the measurements fall at or below this average value, suggesting that the lighting is at the lower limit of 300 lux at times. Room 2 shows a mean illuminance of 345.42 lux, a 37.19 SD, and a CDF of 89%, meaning that 89% of the measurements are at or below this level, reflecting generally suitable lighting with some fluctuations. For Room 3 where it has a mean illuminance of 362.38 lux, SD of 38.58, and a CDF of 95%, indicating that 95% of the measurements are at or below this average, providing a stable environment for visual comfort. Lastly, Room 5 has a mean illuminance of 385.04 lux with an SD of 38.02 and a CDF of 99%, suggesting that the lighting is consistent and meets the standard for nearly the entire observation period. The figure highlights that while Rooms 2, 3, and

5 provide adequate lighting, adjustments in Room 1 could enhance consistency to ensure a more effective working environment.

Figure 18. Classroom Illuminance Level: 15:00 PM – 17:30 PM

Figure 18 illustrates the illuminance levels of four rooms from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, as measured against the GRIHA 2015 standard range of 300 to 500 lux. Room 1 has a mean illuminance of 299.97 lux, a 24.02 SD, and a CDF of 50%, indicating that 50% of the measurements fall at or below this average value, suggesting that the lighting is at the lower limit of 300 lux and may not consistently meet the required standard. Room 2 shows a mean illuminance of 370.02 lux with a corresponding SD of 38.93 and a CDF of 96%, meaning that 96% of the measurements are at or below this level, reflecting generally suitable lighting with minimal fluctuation. Room 3 has a mean illuminance of 288.46 lux, SD of 30.64, and a CDF of 35%, indicating that 35% of the measurements are at or below this average, suggesting that this room consistently falls below the

acceptable range. In addition, Room 5 has a mean illuminance of 346.92 lux for an SD of 22.68 and a CDF of 98%, suggesting that the lighting is consistent and meets the standard for nearly the entire observation period. The figure highlights that while Rooms 2 and 5 provide adequate lighting, adjustments in Room 1 are necessary to ensure consistency, and Room 3 requires improvements to meet the minimum standard of 300 lux.

Figure 19. Room 1 Illuminance Level: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

In Figure 19, Room 1's illuminance levels exhibit noticeable fluctuations throughout the day, reflecting variations in lighting conditions from morning to late afternoon. Between 7:30 and 10:00 AM, the room records a mean illuminance of 367.73 lux with a standard deviation (SD) of 74.10 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 78%, indicating moderate variability but generally sufficient lighting. From 10:00 to 12:30 PM, the mean illuminance slightly increases to 368.03 lux, with a SD of 32.27 and a CDF of 98%, suggesting that the lighting during this period is more stable and meets the standard.

However, after 12:30 PM, the mean illuminance decreases to 307.18 lux, with a SD of 26.70 and a CDF of 61%, signaling a decline in lighting consistency, as some measurements fall below the required 300 lux. Finally, between 15:00 and 17:30 PM, the mean illuminance drops further to 299.97 lux, with a SD of 24.02 and a CDF of 50%, indicating that half of the measurements are below the minimum standard, leading to insufficient lighting. These variations highlight the need for adjustments in Room 1's afternoon lighting to ensure consistent and adequate illumination throughout the day.

Figure 20. Room 2 Illuminance Level: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

In Figure 20, Room 2's illuminance levels display significant variation throughout the day, particularly notable in the early morning hours. Between 7:30 and 10:00 AM, the mean illuminance is 833.88 lux, with a standard deviation (SD) of 578.47 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 10%. During the period from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the mean illuminance decreases to 402.88 lux, with an SD of 68.07 and a CDF of 86%. This

drop suggests a more stable lighting environment, as the illuminance is still relatively high but much more consistent, with a large percentage of measurements clustering around the mean. From 12:30 to 15:00 PM, the mean illuminance further declines to 345.42 lux, with an SD of 37.19 and a CDF of 89%. This indicates a slight decrease in brightness, although the room still maintains adequate lighting levels. Finally, from 15:00 to 17:30 PM, the mean illuminance rises to 370.02 lux, with a SD of 38.93 and a CDF of 96%. This suggests that the lighting becomes more stable again, with most readings remaining consistent and well above the minimum requirements for effective illumination.

The high mean illuminance in the early hours could be attributed to factors such as large windows that allow ample natural light to enter, or the presence of powerful artificial lighting. However, the high variability indicated by the SD highlights the need for better control over lighting conditions in Room 2 to ensure a consistent and comfortable environment for occupants throughout the day.

Figure 21. Room 3 Illuminance Level: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

In Figure 21, Room 3's illuminance levels display a consistent trend throughout the day, reflecting an overall well-lit environment. During the period from 7:30 to 10:00 AM, the mean illuminance is 407.36 lux, with a standard deviation (SD) of 60.23 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 90%. This indicates that a substantial majority of the measurements fall below the average. From 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the mean illuminance slightly decreases to 383.96 lux, with an SD of 45.62 and a CDF of 96%. This reduction indicates a gradual decline in brightness, although the environment remains well-lit. The consistent CDF suggests that the illuminance levels are still largely uniform, providing a suitable level of light for classroom activities. Between 12:30 and 3:00 PM, the mean illuminance further decreases to 362.38 lux, with a SD of 38.58 and a CDF of 95%. This suggests that the room continues to maintain an adequate light level, with a high percentage of measurements remaining below the average, reinforcing the idea of

a consistently illuminated space. However, from 3:00 to 5:30 PM, the mean illuminance drops significantly to 288.46 lux, with a SD of 30.64 and a CDF of 35%. This decline indicates that the lighting levels may become less sufficient as the day progresses, potentially leading to a less favorable environment for learning or work. The lower CDF indicates that fewer measurements fall below this mean, suggesting variability in lighting conditions during this period. Overall, Room 3 maintains a generally well-lit environment throughout the morning and early afternoon, but the significant drop in illuminance during the late afternoon may necessitate adjustments.

Figure 22. Room 5 Illuminance Level: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 22, Room 5's illuminance levels present a distinct pattern throughout the day, characterized by a generally bright and stable lighting environment. During the period from 7:30 to 10:00 AM, the mean illuminance is 455.91 lux, with a standard deviation (SD)

of 73.33 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 71%. This indicates a relatively high level of brightness, although the CDF suggests that a significant portion of the illuminance measurements is below the average, which could be attributed to varying factors such as room layout or window positioning. From 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the mean illuminance decreases to 396.01 lux, an SD of 38.95 and a CDF of 99%. This drop indicates a gradual reduction in brightness, yet the very high CDF suggests that nearly all measurements are above this mean, reflecting consistent and sufficient illumination for classroom activities during this time. In the subsequent period, 12:30 to 3:00 PM, the mean illuminance further decreases to 385.04 lux, with a similar SD of 38.02 and a CDF of 99%. The consistent high CDF continues to indicate a well-lit environment, ensuring that the classroom remains conducive for learning. However, from 3:00 to 5:30 PM, the mean illuminance drops to 346.92 lux, with a SD of 22.68 and a CDF of 98%. Although this represents a decrease in brightness, the high CDF indicates that most illuminance measurements still exceed this mean level, suggesting that the room remains adequately lit even as natural light decreases.

Overall, Room 5 exhibits a strong performance in maintaining suitable illuminance levels throughout the day, with particularly high levels in the morning. The gradual decline in brightness during the afternoon hours suggests that the space may require additional lighting solutions as the day progresses to ensure comfort and productivity for the occupants.

Classroom Illuminance Uniformity Compliance

Figure 23. Classroom Illuminance Uniformity: 7:30 AM – 10:00 AM

Figure 23 illustrates the classroom illuminance uniformity from 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, measured against the ISO/CIE 8995 standard, which sets a minimum average uniformity of 0.7. Room 1 has a uniformity ratio of 0.70 with a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 50% and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.11, indicating that while it meets the minimum acceptable level, half of the measurements fall at or below this average value, suggesting potential inconsistencies in lighting distribution. Room 2 shows a uniformity ratio of 0.57, a CDF of 27%, and an SD of 0.21 indicating that this room does not meet the minimum standard and has a significant portion of measurements falling below this level, which could affect visual comfort. With a uniformity ratio of 0.71, 0.07 SD, and a CDF of 56%, Room 3 appears to meet the minimum average, although a

notable portion of measurements still falls below this average. Lastly, Room 5 has a uniformity ratio of 0.73, 0.11 SD, and a CDF of 61%,

Figure 24. Classroom Illuminance Uniformity: 10:00 AM – 12:30 PM

As what Figure 24 has depicted, it shows the consistency of lighting or illuminance uniformity in the classrooms between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM, compared to the ISO/CIE 8995 guideline specifying a minimum uniformity of 0.7. Room 1 has a uniformity ratio of 0.78, a CDF of 87%, and an SD of 0.07 meaning it meets the minimum criteria thus 87% of the measurements lower than this average value. Room 2 has a uniformity ratio of 0.64 and a CDF of 38% while having an SD of 0.20, shows that it falls below the minimum standard with a substantial number of measurements below this level, potentially impacting visual comfort. As for Room 3 having a uniformity ratio of 0.76, CDF of 86%, and 0.05 SD indicates it is within the average value, the uniform distribution of light in this room is quite appropriate but adjustments to certain factors must be considered in order

to have consistent distribution of light. Lastly for Room 5 with a uniformity ratio of 0.73 and a CDF of 61% with 0.11 SD signifying that it is below the average value yet still within the standard.

Figure 25. Classroom Illuminance Uniformity: 12:30 PM – 15:00 PM

Figure 25 indicates the uniformity of lighting in classrooms between 12:30 PM and 15:00 PM, comparing it to the ISO/CIE 8995 guideline of a minimum uniformity of 0.7. Room 1 of having a uniformity ratio of 0.79, a 0.09 SD with a CDF of 84% and Room 5 with 0.73 ratio, a 0.05 SD and a CDF of 73%, both meeting the standard, as 84% and 73% of these measurements are below the average values. For Room 2, with a ratio of 0.71, a 0.14 SD and a CDF of 53%, nearly reaches half the minimum standard and 53% fall below the range of average value as well but might indicate significant visual comfort issues. Room 3 on the other hand has a ratio of 0.76, a 0.13 SD and a CDF of 68%,

signifying that its even distribution of light is appropriate but still requires adjustments for consistency when it comes to room lightings.

Figure 26. Classroom Illuminance Uniformity: 15:00 PM – 17:30 PM

Figure 26 illustrates the consistency of lighting, specifically the uniformity of illuminance in the classrooms between the hours of 15:00 PM and 17:30 PM. This analysis is compared against the ISO/CIE 8995 guideline, which sets a minimum uniformity standard of 0.7. In Room 1, the uniformity ratio is measured at 0.69, an SD of 0.12 with a CDF of 47%. These figures indicate that Room 1 of the recorded measurements are below this average value, suggesting an unstable lighting environment. Conversely, Room 2 presents a different scenario with a uniformity ratio of 0.70, SD of 0.14 accompanied by a CDF of 50. This data reveals that Room 2 falls half of the minimum standard, and a significant proportion of its measurements are below the average value, which could negatively affect visual comfort to students. Room 3

demonstrates a more favorable lighting situation, featuring a uniformity ratio of 0.72, and SD of 0.09 and a CDF of 59%. These suggest that while Room 3 almost has an even distribution of light, there is still a need for adjustments in certain factors to ensure an even more consistent illumination throughout the space. Lastly, Room 5 shows a uniformity ratio of 0.73, a CDF of 58%, and an SD of 0.14. Although this room is below the average value, it remains within the acceptable standard. Overall, the data across these rooms highlights varying degrees of lighting uniformity, with specific recommendations for improvements in those rooms that fall below the desired criteria. According to Mathalamuthu et al. (2018), avoiding having dark painted walls and furniture's that are obstructing the daylight source will improve the daylighting in the classroom.

Figure 27. Room 1 Illuminance Uniformity: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 27 shows the illuminance uniformity in Room 1 from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, compared to the ISO/CIE 8995 standard, where the minimum uniformity is 0.7. Between 7:30 AM and 10:00 AM, Room 1 recorded a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.70, and SD of 0.11 with a CDF of 50% which indicates that half of the measurements fall at or below this value, suggesting that the uniformity is within the minimum acceptable level. However, from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the illuminance uniformity improved to 0.78, an SD of 0.07 with a CDF of 87%, indicating that 87% of the measurements fall at or below 0.70, indicating a more even light distribution during this period. Between 12:30 PM and 15:00 PM, Room 1 maintained a similar uniformity of 0.79 and SD of 0.09, with a CDF of 84% indicating that 87% of the measurements fall at or below the minimum level, continuing to suggest a consistent light distribution. In contrast, from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, the illuminance uniformity dropped to 0.69 an SD of 0.12 with a CDF of 47% indicating that 47% of the measurements fall at or below the average level, indicating uneven light distribution during the later hours. Overall, this analysis shows that during the early hours, Room 1 is within the minimum acceptable uniformity level and experiences a significant improvement as the day progresses with uniformity levels consistently above the standard, indicating an even lighting distribution. However, in the late afternoon, the uniformity drops below the required level, highlighting potential issues with lighting consistency. This fluctuation suggests the need for adjustments to maintain consistent lighting throughout the entire day.

Figure 28. Room 2 Illuminance Uniformity: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 28 shows the illuminance uniformity measurements for Room 2 between 7:30 AM and 17:30 PM, compared to the ISO/CIE 8995 standard, where the minimum uniformity is 0.7. From 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 2 has a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.57 an SD of 0.21 with a CDF of 27%, indicating that 27% of the values fall at or below this level, indicating uneven light distribution. Between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM, the uniformity increases to 0.64 an SD of 0.20, with 38% of the values at or below the average, suggesting continued instability in light distribution. From 12:30 PM to 3:00 PM, the uniformity improves to 0.71 an SD of 0.14, with a CDF of 53%, indicating that 53% of the values falls at or below this level, indicating a more even light distribution during this period. Lastly, from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, the uniformity reaches 0.70, an SD of 0.14, meeting the minimum requirement, although 50% of the values still fall at or below the average, indicating possible lighting inconsistencies. Overall, this analysis shows

fluctuations in the illuminance uniformity of Room 2 throughout the day, with the light distribution being uneven during the morning and gradually improving in the afternoon. These inconsistencies, especially in the morning, indicate the need for modifications to the lighting system to achieve a more consistent and balanced light distribution throughout the day.

Figure 29. Room 3 Illuminance Uniformity: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 29 shows the illuminance uniformity measurements for Room 9 from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, compared to the ISO/CIE 8995 standard where the minimum uniformity is 0.7. The data collected from 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM indicates that Room 3 has a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.71 an SD of 0.07 with a (CDF) of 56%, indicating that 56% of the measurements fall at or below this average, suggesting a relatively even light distribution. From 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the uniformity improves to 0.76 and SD of 0.05, with a CDF of 88%, indicating that 88% of the measurements are at or below the average,

reflecting enhanced lighting distribution during this period. Between 12:30 PM and 15:00 PM, the average illuminance uniformity remains at 0.76 an SD of 0.13, with a CDF of 68% which indicates that 68% of the values fall at or below this average level. Lastly, from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, Room 3 shows a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.72 an SD of 0.09, with a CDF of 59%, indicating that 59% of the measurements are at or below this average level, suggesting consistent light distribution during this timeframe. Overall, this analysis indicates that measurements consistently meet or exceed the ISO/CIE 8995 standard, with the highest uniformity observed between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM. However, despite these improvements, the data indicates variability at certain times, suggesting a need for improvement in the lighting setup to achieve a consistent and uniform lighting distribution.

Figure 30. Room 5 Illuminance Uniformity: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 30 shows the illuminance uniformity measurements for Room 5 from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, compared to the ISO/CIE 8995 standard with a minimum uniformity of

0.7. From 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 5 shows a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.73, an SD of 0.11 with a (CDF) of 61%, indicating that 61% of the measurements fall at or below the average level, suggesting a relatively even light distribution. From 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, Room 5 maintains an illuminance uniformity of 0.73 an SD of 0.11, with the same CDF of 61%, showing a consistent light distribution. Between 12:30 PM and 15:00 PM, the measurement shows that Room 5 has an average uniformity of 0.73 an SD of 0.05 and a CDF of 73% which indicates that Room 5 meets the minimum acceptable level. Lastly, from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, Room 5 shows a mean illuminance uniformity of 0.73 an SD of 0.14, with a CDF of 58%, which indicates that 58% of the measurements are at or below this average level, suggesting an even lighting distribution during this timeframe. This analysis shows that the illuminance uniformity in Room 5 shows consistent lighting levels throughout the day, with measurements consistently meeting the ISO/CIE 8995 standard. The average uniformity remains stable at 0.73 across all timeframes, indicating a generally even light distribution. However, the CDF values reveal slight variations, particularly in the later afternoon, suggesting that while the room's lighting is within the acceptable level, there may still be opportunities for improvement to enhance the uniformity of the classroom.

Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance Compliance

Figure 31. Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance: 7:30 AM – 10:00 AM

Figure 31 shows the results of wall surface reflectance within classrooms between 7:30 AM and 10:00 AM. This assessment is compared to the CIBSE Code for lighting which establishes a minimum reflectance standard of 0.5 to 0.8. In Room 1, the surface reflectance ratio within this room is recorded at 0.72, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.12 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 71%. These metrics indicate that a significant number of measurements in Room 1 fall below the average but is within the reflectance standard. In contrast, Room 2 exhibits a surface reflectance ratio of 0.92, an SD of 0.34, and a CDF of 25%, Room 3 of having a reflectance ratio of 1.05, an SD of 0.63, and a CDF of 15%, as well as Room 5 of having a reflectance ratio of 0.95, a CDF of 24%, and an SD of 0.30. Data shows that Rooms 2, 3, and 5 exceeded the maximum standard surface reflectance which is 0.8, yet a considerable portion of its measurements

still falls short of the average. This is due to the structure within this room that has lesser furniture and contributes minimal shadowing thus exceeded the standard on wall surface reflectance.

Overall, the analysis of these classrooms reveals varying degrees of wall surface reflectance, pointing to the need for specific improvements in areas that surpassed the desired criteria. The concept of wall surface reflectance refers to how effectively the walls reflect light, which can greatly influence the overall brightness and quality of illumination in the room, thereby affecting the comfort and productivity of the occupants.

Figure 32. Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance: 10:00 AM – 12:30 PM

Figure 32 shows the Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM, compared to the standard reflectance ratio set by the CIBSE Code for Lighting, which specifies acceptable reflectance between 0.5 and 0.8. Room 1 has a mean

reflectance of 0.68 with a standard deviation of 0.06 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 98%, indicating that nearly all measurements fall close to the mean and comfortably within the acceptable standard. Room 2 has a reflectance mean of 0.73, an SD of 0.10, and a CDF of 75%, also within the standard. Room 3 has a reflectance ratio of 0.86, exceeding the upper limit, with an SD of 0.22, and a CDF of 34%, which is right at the upper limit but with noticeable variability. Room 5 has a mean reflectance of 0.80, an SD of 0.14 and a CDF of 48%, indicating that a significant portion of the measurements surpass the standard. While Room 1 and Room 2 are within the acceptable range, Rooms 3 and 5 exceed the upper limit, suggesting that their higher reflectance values may require adjustments, such as surface treatments or alterations in room configuration, to better align with the standard.

Figure 33. Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance: 12:30 PM – 15:00 PM

In Figure 33, the classroom wall surface reflectance between 12:30 PM and 15:00 PM is evaluated against the CIBSE reflectance standard of 0.5 to 0.8. Room 1 has a mean reflectance of 0.74 with a standard deviation of 0.20 and a CDF of 50%, indicating that half of the measurements fall below the average but are still within the standard range. Room 2 shows a mean reflectance of 0.78 with an SD of 0.11 and a CDF of 57%, reflecting consistent lighting within the standard. Room 3 has a mean reflectance of 0.83, an SD of 0.28, and a CDF of 34%, meaning a significant portion of the measurements exceed the upper limit of 0.8 as well as room 5 shows a mean reflectance of 0.77 with an SD of 0.26 and a CDF of 40%, with most measurements remaining within the desired range. Overall, rooms 1, 2, and 5 demonstrate satisfactory reflectance, while Room 3 exceeds the recommended standard.

Figure 34. Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance: 15:00 PM – 17:30 PM

In Figure 34, the classroom wall surface reflectance from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM compares to the CIBSE standard range of 0.5 to 0.8. Room 1 has a mean reflectance of 0.66, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.16 and a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 65%, suggesting that most measurements remain close to the mean. Room 2 has a mean reflectance of 0.75, an SD of 0.15, and a CDF of 58%, indicating stable reflectance within the acceptable range. Room 3, with a mean reflectance of 0.98, an SD of 0.30, and a CDF of 22%, shows that the majority of measurements exceed the upper limit of 0.8, indicating highly reflective surfaces. Lastly, Room 5 has a mean reflectance of 0.87, an SD of 0.27, and a CDF of 31%, with many measurements surpassing the standard. This analysis highlights that Rooms 3 and 5 exceed the upper limit, whereas Rooms 1 and 2 maintain reflectance levels within the CIBSE standard.

Figure 35. Room 1 Wall Surface Reflectance: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 35 presents the wall surface reflectance measurements for Room 1 from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, in relation to the CIBSE Code for lighting with a minimum reflectance standard of 0.5 to 0.8. From 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 1 achieves a mean surface reflectance of 0.72, an SD of 0.12 with a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 71%, indicating that 71% of the measurements fall below the average value, having a stable wall surface reflectance during this time. Between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM, the mean surface reflectance has resulted to 0.68 an SD of 0.06 with the CDF of 98%. From 12:30 PM to 3:00 PM, the average surface reflectance on walls went 0.74 an SD of 0.20, but the CDF decreases to 50%, suggesting that Room 1 meets the minimum acceptable standard. Lastly, from 3:00 PM to 5:30 PM, the mean surface reflectance was 0.66 an SD of 0.16, with a CDF of 65%, indicating that 65% of the measurements are below this average level. Overall, for Room 1, the peak of wall surface reflectance is during the mid-days about 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM. However, the CDF values indicate slight fluctuations, especially in the late afternoon, highlighting potential areas for improvement to further enhance classroom surface reflectance on walls such as removing barriers of light in reflecting to walls because Room 1 has unfortunately several cabinets and other furniture that creates shadows and minimizes the wall surface reflectance within the area.

Figure 36. Room 2 Wall Surface Reflectance: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 36 illustrates the wall surface reflectance results for Room 2 throughout the time frame of 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, in connection with the CIBSE Code for Lighting, which stipulates a minimum reflectance standard ranging from 0.5 to 0.8. During the period from 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 2 records an average surface reflectance of 0.92 an SD of 0.34, accompanied by a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 25%. This indicates that 25% of the reflectance measurements fall below this average value. As the measurements progress from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, the mean surface reflectance slightly decreases to 0.73 an SD of 0.10, yet the CDF rises significantly to 75%, signifying that nearly all measurements are below this average level, both increased in mean reflectance and the CDF during this period. Moving into the next segment from 12:30 PM to 3:00 PM, the average surface reflectance increases to 0.78 an SD of 0.11, but the CDF drops to 57%, demonstrating that Room 1 successfully meets the minimum acceptable

standard during for overall result. Lastly, from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, the mean reflectance returns to 0.75 an SD of 0.15, accompanied by a CDF of 58%, indicating that 58% of the measurements are below this average. In summary, Room 2 has greater means of wall surface reflectance due to having less furniture that can potentially eliminate reflectance. But, during the first period in the morning and last periods in the afternoon shows a decrease in mean as well as the CDF pertaining that there is lesser light that reflects on walls at these times.

Figure 37. Room 3 Wall Surface Reflectance: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 37 shows the wall surface reflectance data collected for Room 3 over the time period extending from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM. This data is analyzed in accordance with the CIBSE Code for Lighting, which has the minimum acceptable reflectance level that should fall within a range of 0.5 to 0.8. During the initial time frame, from 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 3 demonstrates an impressive average reflectance of 1.05 and an SD

of 0.63. Alongside this high average, the cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) is recorded at 15%. This means that the reflectance measurements taken during this period are below the average value of, highlighting a relatively high level of light being reflected off the surfaces in the room at this early hour. For the next time period, from 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM, there is a slight decrease in the average surface reflectance, which drops to 0.86 and an SD of 0.22. However, during this same timeframe, the CDF increases significantly to 34% suggesting an increase in overall light reflectivity compared to the earlier period. Consecutively, from 12:30 PM to 3:00 PM, the average reflectance sees a slight rebound, decreasing to 0.83 and an SD of 0.28 with still the same CDF of 34%, which means that the reflectance measurements fall below this average level. Finally, during the last interval from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM, the average reflectance increases 0.98 and an SD of 0.30 but a decrease in CDF of 22%, indicating that 22% of the measurements taken are below this average value. This suggests a persistent reduction in the reflectance as the day progresses towards afternoon. This performance suggests that Room 3 generally meets the minimum reflectance standards outlined by the CIBSE guidelines throughout this segment.

Figure 38. Room 5 Wall Surface Reflectance: 7:30 AM – 17:30 PM

Figure 38 shows the wall surface reflectance outcomes for Room 5 from 7:30 AM to 17:30 PM, comparing it to the CIBSE Code of Lighting, which sets a minimum reflectance standard of 0.5 to 0.8. From 7:30 AM to 10:00 AM, Room 5 showed an average reflectance of 0.95 and an SD of 0.30, with a cumulative distribution frequency (CDF) of 24%, indicating that 24% of the measurements fell below this average, meaning the surface reflectance in this period had exceeded the standard. Next, between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM, the mean reflectance decreased slightly to 0.80 and an SD of 0.14, while the CDF rose to 48% which means, as compared to the other rooms, it is mostly high in reflectance to walls at this time. Lastly, at 12:30 PM to 15:00 PM, the mean reflectance went 0.77 an SD of 0.26 and a CDF of 40% and from 15:00 PM to 17:30 PM the mean reflectance has increased to 0.87 and an SD of 0.27 with a CDF of 31% indicating that Room 5 is the same from the previous rooms when it come to wall

reflectance having a minimal increase at 10:00 AM to 12:30 PM. Overall, the highest reflectance occurs around midday, specifically between 10:00 AM and 12:30 PM. However, the CDF values demonstrate some inconsistent changes, particularly in the late afternoon, suggesting areas for improvement in enhancing wall reflectance.

SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE AMONG CLASSROOMS BASED ON MEAN SCORES FOR VISUAL COMFORT PARAMETERS

This section explores the variations in mean scores for visual comfort parameters among the classrooms and assesses their statistical significance.

Classroom Illuminance Levels

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis; $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_5$

(There is no significant difference between the mean illuminance levels in Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5.)

Alternative Hypothesis; H_a : At least one mean illuminance level (μ) is different from the others.

(There is a significant difference between the mean illuminance levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, or Room 5.)

Table 18. Analysis of Variance of Classroom Illuminance Levels

	DF	Mean Square	F statistics	p-value	Decision
Groups (between groups)	3	267,203.6644	6.1358	0.0005	Reject Null Hypothesis
Error (within groups)	236	43,548.1633			
Total	239				

There was a statistically significant difference in illuminance levels among the four classrooms, as determined by one-way ANOVA, $F = 6.1358$, with a p-value of 0.0005, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05 (Table 18). This suggests that at least one classroom's illuminance level differs significantly from the others.

Table 19. Post-hoc Tukey HSD Results of Classroom Illuminance Levels

Pairwise Comparison	Tukey HSD Q statistic	Tukey HSD p-value	Tukey HSD inference
Room 1 vs Room 2	5.6540	0.0010053	** p<0.01
Room 1 vs Room 3	0.9208	0.8999947	insignificant
Room 1 vs Room 5	2.2362	0.3924653	insignificant
Room 2 vs Room 3	4.7331	0.0052293	** p<0.01
Room 2 vs Room 5	3.4178	0.0768364	insignificant
Room 3 vs Room 5	1.3153	0.7635483	insignificant

The Tukey HSD post-hoc analysis reveals a significant difference in illuminance levels between Room 1 (335.73 lux) and Room 2 (488.05 lux) and between Room 2 (488.05 lux) and Room 3 (360.54 lux), as shown in the Table 19. No significant differences were found between Room 1 (335.73 lux) and Room 3 (360.54 lux), Room 1 (335.73 lux) and Room 5 (395.97 lux), Room 2 (488.05 lux) and Room 5 (395.97 lux), or Room 3 (360.54 lux) and Room 5 (395.97 lux).

In summary, the ANOVA results suggest that there are significant differences in illuminance levels among the four classrooms overall. The Tukey HSD post-hoc analysis pinpoints the specific differences, revealing that Room 1 and Room 2, as well as Room 2 and Room 3, have significantly different illuminance levels. However, Rooms 1, 3, and 5

appear to have similar lighting conditions, as their illuminance levels are not significantly different.

Classroom Illuminance Uniformity

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis; Ho: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_5$

(There is statistically significant difference between the mean illuminance uniformity levels in Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5.)

Alternative Hypothesis; Ha: At least one mean illuminance uniformity (μ) is different from the others.

(There is a significant difference between the mean illuminance uniformity levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5)

Table 20. Analysis of Variance of Classroom Illuminance Uniformity

	DF	Mean Square	F statistics	p-value	Decision
Groups (between groups)	3	0.0970	5.6884	0.0009	Reject Null Hypothesis
Error (within groups)	236	0.0171			
Total	239				

The results of the one-way ANOVA indicate a statistically significant difference in illuminance uniformity among the four classrooms, $F=6.6884$, with a p-value of 0.0009, which is well below the alpha level of 0.05 (Table 20). This suggests that at least one

classroom has a significantly different level of illuminance uniformity compared to the others.

Table 21. Post-hoc Tukey HSD Results of Classroom Illuminance Uniformity.

Pairwise Comparison	Tukey HSD Q statistic	Tukey HSD p-value	Tukey HSD inference
Room 1 vs Room 2	4.8860	0.0036263	** p<0.01
Room 1 vs Room 3	0.0326	0.8999947	insignificant
Room 1 vs Room 5	0.4387	0.8999947	insignificant
Room 2 vs Room 3	4.9186	0.0033496	** p<0.01
Room 2 vs Room 5	4.4474	0.0100670	* p<0.05
Room 3 vs Room 5	0.4712	0.8999947	insignificant

The Tukey HSD post-hoc analysis reveals significant differences in illuminance uniformity between Room 1 (0.8775) and Room 2 (0.7500), between Room 2 (0.7500) and Room 3 (0.8400), and between Room 2 (0.7500) and Room 5 (0.8650), as shown in the Table 21. In contrast, no significant differences were found between Room 1 (0.8775) and Room 3 (0.8400), Room 1 (0.8775) and Room 5 (0.8650), or Room 3 (0.8400) and Room 5 (0.8650).

These results indicate that Room 2 exhibits unique characteristics in terms of illuminance uniformity, differentiating it from the other classrooms. Rooms 1, 3, and 5, on the other hand, appear to have similar levels of illuminance uniformity, suggesting that their lighting conditions are more consistent.

Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis; Ho: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_5$

(There is significant difference between the mean wall surface reflectance levels in Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5.)

Alternative Hypothesis; Ha: At least one mean illuminance level (μ) is different from the others.

(There is a significant difference between the mean wall surface reflectance levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5.)

Table 22. Analysis of Variance of Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance

	DF	Mean Square	F statistics	p-value	Decision
Groups (between groups)	3	0.5876	10.8789	1.0158e-06	Reject Null Hypothesis
Error (within groups)	236	0.0540			
Total	239				

The results of the One-Way ANOVA indicate a statistically significant difference in wall surface reflectance among the four classrooms, with $F = 10.8789$ and a p-value of $1.0158e-06$, which is significantly lower than the conventional alpha level of 0.05 (Table 22). This suggests that at least one classroom has a significantly different level of wall surface reflectance compared to the others.

Table 23. Post-hoc Tukey HSD Results of Classroom Wall Surface Reflectance

Pairwise Comparison	Tukey HSD Q statistic	Tukey HSD p-value	Tukey HSD inference
Room 1 vs Room 2	2.0460	0.4724668	insignificant
Room 1 vs Room 3	7.4310	0.0010053	** p<0.01
Room 1 vs Room 5	5.2145	0.0015962	** p<0.01
Room 2 vs Room 3	5.3849	0.0010227	** p<0.01
Room 2 vs Room 5	3.1685	0.1155855	insignificant
Room 3 vs Room 5	2.2164	0.4006318	insignificant

The Tukey HSD post-hoc analysis reveals notable disparities in wall surface reflectance among the classrooms, as show in Table 23. Significant differences were found between Room 1 (0.7006) and Room 3 (0.9275), as well as between Room 1 (0.7006) and Room 5 (0.8469), both with p-values less than 0.01. Additionally, there is a significant difference between Room 2 (0.7931) and Room 3 (0.9275), also with a p-value below 0.01. However, no significant differences were detected between Room 1 (0.7006) and Room 2 (0.7931), Room 2 (0.7931) and Room 5 (0.8469), or Room 3 (0.9275) and Room 5 (0.8469).

These results indicate that Rooms 3 and 5 have significantly different wall surface reflectance compared to Room 1, suggesting that the lighting conditions in these classrooms may be influenced by the reflective properties of their walls. Room 2 does not show significant differences in reflectance when compared to Room 1 or Room 5, indicating that its reflective properties are more similar to those of Room 1.

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the study, highlights the key findings, draws conclusions from the analysis, and offers recommendations for improving illuminance quality in university classrooms.

SUMMARY

This research study was conducted to assess the illuminance quality in the classrooms of the College of Engineering, located in the newly constructed building of Cebu Technological University (CTU) Moalboal Campus. The purpose of the study was to provide a descriptive analysis of the lighting conditions and offer suggestions for enhancing visual comfort, thereby contributing to improved learning environments. Data were gathered on various lighting and visual comfort parameters, including illuminance levels, illuminance uniformity, and wall surface reflectance.

A descriptive statistical technique was employed for each parameter to assess the collected data from four classrooms, identifying patterns, trends, and variations using Normal Distribution (Bell Curve) in relation to the established standards. Furthermore, statistical treatment was utilized to distinguish the assessed classrooms based on these visual comfort parameters. A One-Way ANOVA was conducted, followed by a Tukey HSD test to evaluate significant differences across the observed data. The integration of the standards provided by GRIHA V-2015, ISO/CIE 8995, and the CIBSE Code for Lighting offers a robust framework for evaluating lighting in learning environments and ensures adherence to international standards for task performance and visual comfort.

The findings revealed that Room 2 exhibited the highest illuminance levels but had the least uniformity. In terms of compliance with established standards, Room 5 achieved the highest illuminance level compliance at 92%, while Room 2 recorded the lowest uniformity compliance at 42%. Additionally, wall surface reflectance varied among the rooms, with Room 3 having the lowest at 26% and Room 1 the highest at 71%. Variations in fixtures and their arrangement across the classrooms potentially influenced and contributed to the overall illuminance quality

FINDINGS

After the data were gathered, classified, tabulated, computed, and interpreted, the following findings were drawn:

SOP 1: Classroom Profiles

All assessed classrooms were located in the College of Engineering Department at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus, specifically situated on the fourth floor of the newly constructed building. The assessments were conducted in March and April, during which stable weather conditions were experienced during the assessment, thereby minimizing further variations in the observed values. In terms of external physical structure, all classrooms share similar dimensions, window characteristics (jalousie and sliding), and window orientation (both facing northeast and west). Additionally, all classrooms are equipped with identical lighting fixtures (six 18-watt double fluorescent lights with louvers) and similar placement.

Internally, all classrooms have white-painted walls, which significantly contribute to the ambiance and illuminance quality. Rooms 1 and 2 feature identical white curtains for jalousie windows, while Rooms 3 and 5 are equipped with matching pink blind curtains and have the highest number of computers compared to the other rooms. However, the arrangement of furniture varies across the classrooms. Room 1 contains the most furniture, followed by Room 3, while Room 2 has the least furniture, ensuring that student chairs are well distributed within the classroom. According to Mousavi et al. (2017), indoor environmental quality, particularly concerning thermal and visual comfort, can be influenced by various furniture arrangements within buildings. The study demonstrated

that the illuminance levels in a furnished room can vary significantly compared to those in an unfurnished room. Each furniture arrangement creates a specific light distribution; therefore, furniture can significantly influence the indoor illuminance level. Furthermore, the importance of understanding the effect of color on the quality of natural lighting, which can impact the surrounding environment and human performance (Maslizam et al., 2023). In a detailed examination of classroom environments, Angelaki (2020) measured the reflectance values of various surfaces, including those affected by electronic devices like computer monitors. The findings indicate that the presence and arrangement of such appliances can alter the reflectance characteristics of surrounding surfaces, thereby influencing the overall lighting quality and uniformity in classrooms. Therefore, the findings suggest that preferences for wall paint, curtain color, fixture and arrangement, as well as the presence of electronic equipment, may significantly influence the overall illuminance quality of the classrooms.

SOP 2: Assessment of Classrooms Using Visual Comfort Parameters: Illuminance Level, Illuminance Uniformity, and Wall Surface Reflectance

The assessment of classroom illuminance quality utilized visual comfort parameters, including illuminance level, illuminance uniformity, and wall surface reflectance, with observed values obtained primarily using a lux meter. The findings revealed that the values for each parameter decreased over time as sunlight diminished, indicating that natural lighting greatly contributes to the classrooms' illuminance quality. In terms of illuminance level, Room 2 recorded the highest illuminance level, while Room 1 had the lowest. Regarding illuminance uniformity, Room 2 exhibited the lowest uniformity, implying that it possessed uneven light distribution. Lastly, concerning wall

surface reflectance, Room 1 had the lowest value, whereas Room 3 recorded the highest value. According to Suh et al. (2022), indoor light quality in classrooms is significantly influenced by sunlight entering through windows, as glass allows natural light to penetrate the room, even when closed. This means that sunlight can still illuminate the space. Consequently, classroom illuminance fluctuates based on outdoor light conditions, including the time of day and weather. Furthermore, Maesano (2016) highlights that classrooms with windows or skylights facing north receive more daylight, resulting in subtle changes in light levels and color texture throughout the day. Different window orientations can create specific areas of concentrated light.

SOP 3: Compliance of Observed Visual Comfort Parameters with Established Standards

The assessment of illuminance quality in university classrooms, as indicated by the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) values, demonstrates significant discrepancies in adherence to established lighting standards. The findings indicate that the classrooms show varying degrees of compliance with the GRIHA V – 2015 standard for illuminance levels, which recommends a range of 300 to 500 lux. Room 1 had a compliance rate of 72%, Room 2 with 70%, Room 3 attained 79%, and Room 5 surpassed expectations with 92%. While Room 5 demonstrates strong compliance, Rooms 1 and 2 fall short of optimal lighting conditions.

In terms of illuminance uniformity, classrooms present a significant concern. According to the ISO/CIE 8995 standard, which sets a minimum uniformity ratio (U_o) of 0.7, the results show that Room 1 exhibited a compliance rate of 67%, Room 2 had a low compliance rate of 42%, Room 3 with 68%, and Room 5 recorded 63%. The low value

for Room 2 indicates a lack of uniform light distribution, which could lead to discomfort and visual strain. The other rooms also show values below the ideal threshold, suggesting the need for improved lighting distribution to create a more conducive learning environment.

The lower compliance percentages in Room 2, both in terms of illuminance level and uniformity, are likely influenced by external factors such as daylight, especially during the morning hours. Room 2's more open layout, coupled with less furniture compared to the other rooms, allows for greater natural light infiltration. This increased daylight exposure leads to uneven lighting distribution, contributing to the lower compliance percentages. Additionally, the classroom fixtures may reduce the ability to diffuse light effectively, exacerbating the inconsistencies in the measured illuminance.

The analysis of wall surface reflectance, according to the CIBSE Code for Lighting, which specifies a reflectance range of 0.5 to 0.8, reveals that Room 1 had a compliance rate of 71%, Room 2 demonstrated 54%, Room 3 with 26%, and Room 5 recorded 36%. The low compliance percentage in Rooms 3 and 5 may suggest a diminished ability to reflect light, as darker surfaces or obstructions absorb more light rather than reflecting it back into the room. However, despite Room 5's lower surface reflectance, it achieved 92% compliance with illuminance level standards. This indicates that factors other than wall reflectance, such as effective lighting fixtures, window placement, and the room layout, have contributed to maintaining adequate lighting conditions. Although both Rooms 3 and 5 feature light pink curtains and internal partitions that may reduce reflectance, Room 5's high compliance suggests that its overall lighting is sufficient.

In summary, while some classrooms demonstrate adequate compliance with illuminance levels, significant issues remain regarding illuminance uniformity and wall surface reflectance. These findings highlight the need for targeted improvements in classroom lighting to ensure adherence to established standards.

SOP 4: Significant Differences Among Classrooms Based on Mean Values Categorized by Visual Comfort Parameters

H_a: There is a significant difference between the mean illuminance levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, or Room 5.

The results of the analysis indicate significant differences in illuminance levels among the four classrooms. The findings reveal that Room 2 is significantly different from Rooms 1 and 3, boasting significantly higher illuminance levels. However, no significant differences were found among Rooms 1, 3, and 5, indicating comparable lighting conditions. Room 1 consistently falls short of the established standard, particularly in the late afternoon. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions in Room 1 to ensure compliance with the standard. As observed, the illuminance level in Room 2 is most likely influenced by daylight, especially in the morning, due to the absence of obstructions outside and the fact that the room contains fewer fixtures compared to Room 1. According to the study by Mousavi et al. (2018), daylight recorded the highest fluctuations among all variables in the case room. The amount of daylight experienced significant variations or changes compared to other variables, suggesting that daylight levels were not consistent and were influenced by factors such as time of day, weather conditions, or the layout of the room. Additionally, various furniture layouts in a residential

working room may slightly reduce the extreme quantity of indoor daylight. This implies that while furniture arrangements can affect indoor daylight levels, they may not completely eliminate high levels of daylight but can mitigate its intensity to some extent.

H_a: There is a significant difference between the mean illuminance uniformity levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5

The analysis results underscore the distinct differences in illuminance uniformity, particularly emphasizing Room 2 which is significantly different compared to the other classrooms. In contrast, Rooms 1, 3, and 5 demonstrate similar levels of uniformity, suggesting a more consistent and stable lighting environment throughout the day. These findings indicate the necessity of improving light distribution in Room 2.

According to Mousavi et al. (2018), and Yunitsyna and Toska (2023), extreme outdoor lighting can increase indoor daylight levels, particularly in rooms facing east and west. Furthermore, the study by Mousavi et al. (2018) found that varying furniture layouts reduced daylight availability by around 11%. Additionally, the arrangement of furniture and equipment affects the amount of diffused light within the rooms, which plays a key role in light distribution. Furniture placement can block sunlight from reaching deeper parts of a room, resulting in less uniform lighting. While furniture arrangements can slightly reduce excessive daylight, they may also negatively affect indoor lighting quality compared to unfurnished spaces.

H_a: There is a significant difference between the mean wall surface reflectance levels in at least one of the classrooms: Room 1, Room 2, Room 3, and Room 5.

The analysis results indicate significant differences in wall surface reflectance among the classrooms, particularly distinguishing Rooms 3 and 5 from Room 1. These rooms feature pink curtains, which may contribute to their lower reflectance values compared to the other rooms. Darker or less reflective surfaces absorb more light rather than reflecting it back into the room. According to Maslizam et al. (2023), walls painted white and fixtures that feature light colors, preferably white, yield higher illuminance readings than those in darker colors. Furthermore, the small partitions within these classrooms may also contribute to this effect. As a result, the reflective properties in Rooms 3 and 5 are significantly different from those in other classrooms, particularly when compared to Room 1. Thus, the lower reflectance values in Rooms 3 and 5 suggest a need for brighter wall colors or reflective finishes to improve light distribution and enhance overall illuminance levels.

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive assessment of classroom illuminance quality at Cebu Technological University's Moalboal Campus New Building, College of Engineering, provided significant insights into the factors that influence visual comfort parameters such as illuminance levels, uniformity, and wall surface reflectance. The findings implies that, while all classrooms have comparable structural characteristics, variances in interior factors like curtain color, furniture arrangement, and the presence of electronic equipment have a substantial impact on overall illumination quality.

In particular, Room 2 emerged with the highest illuminance level, likely benefiting from minimal daylight exposure primary due to its location, layout and fewer obstructions. Conversely, Rooms 1 and 2 showed inadequacies in accordance with established lighting standards, particularly in terms of illuminance uniformity, highlighting the crucial need for focused interventions. The research found considerable disparities in wall surface reflectance among classrooms, particularly in Rooms 3 and 5, which diminish light reflection capabilities

These findings advocate an integrated approach for enhancing classroom illuminance quality, such as using brighter wall colors, optimizing furniture layouts, and upgrading lighting fixtures to improve illuminance levels, uniformity, and surface reflectance capabilities. By addressing these factors, the institution may foster a more conducive learning environment that encourages student involvement and academic performance. Further research may be necessary to explore further approaches for improving overall classroom environmental quality for enhanced visual comfort.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from the classroom illuminance assessment, the following recommendations aim to enhance the overall visual comfort and learning environment. Room 5, exhibited a 92% compliance rate with established illuminance standards, outperforming other classrooms. Despite this commendable performance, there are several areas for improvement.

To optimize the existing bright environment, consider enhancing the reflectivity of the space through the addition of light-colored accessories, such as furniture or decorative elements, that complement the white walls. Additionally, replacing existing curtains with lighter, more translucent options can help maximize the intake of natural light while maintaining privacy. Incorporating sheer curtains or adjustable blinds will further aid in controlling glare throughout the day.

Reassessing the furniture arrangement is also crucial. Utilizing modular furniture can create flexible layouts tailored to various classroom activities. Upgrading to energy-efficient LED lighting with adjustable brightness settings will provide varying light levels according to different times of day or specific tasks, while task lighting at workstations can enhance illumination for focused activities. Integrating these lighting solutions will allow classrooms to adapt to different environments, particularly based on occupancy and time of day, maintaining optimal lighting conditions with energy efficiency focused. By implementing these improvements, Room 5 can further enhance its already favorable illumination quality, , fostering a more conducive and visually comfortable learning environment.

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APPENDICES

Appendices A. TRANSMITTAL LETTER

Republic of the Philippines
CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY
MOALBOAL CAMPUS
 Poblacion West, Moalboal Cebu
 Tel Nos. (032) 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383
 Fax Nos. 474-8196; 474-8104; 474-8383
 Website: <http://www.ctu.edu.ph>

College of Engineering Faculty
 Cebu Technological University - Moalboal Campus
 Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

March 8, 2024

Ma'am/ Sir;

Greetings of peace and love!

We, the Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering (BSIE) 3B-Day students would like to proceed in gathering of data for our **Research Writing** subject and comply the needed information that would support our study. The study is entitled **"Illuminance Quality Assessment in the CTU Moalboal Campus: A Comprehensive Analysis for Enhanced Visual Comfort"**

We would like to inform the College of Engineering Faculty that we will be using the IE Rooms 1, 2, 3, and 5 for a short span of time and we will be using devices for accurate measurements that is why we have to utilize the said rooms without any hindrances that could potentially cause some errors- which will be monitored and avoided as much as possible. This will be done on the 10th Day of March 2024, Sunday for the purpose of lesser student population and more rooms available.

Your consideration to this important matter will greatly contribute to making our paper a success. We look forward to humble responses.

Thank you and have a great day ahead.

Sincerely,

RONA CATALIWALAAN

LUCYANNE MARIE H. MORENO

CHIERKY ANN B. OLIVARES

DIANA JINN SATINA

Noted by:

JESSIE M. CASIA, IE
 Research Writing Adviser

Approved by:

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, CIE, MSIE
 Research Writing Instructor
 Dean, College of Engineering

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College of Engineering Faculty
 Cebu Technological University - Moalboal Campus
 Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

March 11, 2024

Ma'am/ Sir,

Greetings of peace and love!

The Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering (BSIE) 3B- Day students would like to proceed in gathering of data for our **Research Writing** subject and comply the needed information that would support our study. The study is entitled "*Illuminance Quality Assessment in the CTU Moalboal Campus New Building Classrooms: A Comprehensive Analysis for Enhanced Visual Comfort*".

We would like to inform the College of Engineering Faculty that we will be using the IE Rooms 1, 2, 3, and 5 here at the **New Building 4th Floor of Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus**. The gathering of data will take a short span of time and we will be using devices for accurate measurements that is why we have to utilize the said rooms without any hindrances that could potentially cause some errors- which will be monitored and avoided as much as possible. This will be done on the 11th to 14th Day of March 2024, Monday to Thursday.

Time Schedule per Room

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday
IE Room 1	10-12pm 4-5pm		1-3pm	8-10am
IE Room 2	none	none	none	none
IE Room 3	1-3pm		4-5pm	8-10am 10-12pm
IE Room 5		8-10am		

Your consideration to this important matter will greatly contribute to making our paper a success. We look forward to humble responses.

Thank you and have a great day ahead.

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Sincerely,

RONA CATALIWALAAN

LUCYANNE MARIE H. MORENO

CHERRY ANN B. OLIVARES

DIANA JINN SATINA

Noted by:

JESSIE M. CASIA, IE
Methodology of Research Adviser

Approved by:

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, CIE, MSIE
Methodology of Research Instructor
Dean, College of Engineering

Republic of the Philippines
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College of Engineering Faculty/Instructors:

Name of Instructors	Signature
Jessie Rey F. Avenido	
Jessie M. Casia	
Jiffa Marie R. Mabanto	
Dante T. Vallente	
Jhyanyrose Y. Domosmog	
Limic M. dela Calzada II	
Leah Mae Cababat	
Jeam Clyde Baird	
Benjamin D. Rubin	

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College of Engineering Faculty
 Cebu Technological University - Moalboal Campus
 Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

April 5, 2024

Ma'am/ Sir,

Greetings of peace and love!

The Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering (BSIE) 3B- Day students would like to proceed in the final gathering of data for our **Research Writing** subject and comply the needed information that would support our study. The study is entitled "*Illuminance Quality Assessment in the CTU Moalboal Campus New Building Classrooms: A Comprehensive Analysis for Enhanced Visual Comfort*".

We would like to inform the College of Engineering Faculty that we will be using the IE Rooms 1, 2, 3, and 5 here at the **New Building 4th Floor of Cebu Technological University Moalboal Campus**. The gathering of data will take the entire time of the day and we will be using devices for accurate measurements that is why we have to utilize the said rooms without any hindrances that could potentially cause some errors- which will be monitored and avoided as much as possible. This will be done on the 6th and 7th Day of April 2024, Saturday and Sunday.

Your consideration to this important matter will greatly contribute to making our paper a success. We look forward to humble responses.

Thank you and have a great day ahead.

Sincerely,

 RONA CATALIWALAAN

 LUCYANNE MARIE H. MORENO

 CHIERRY ANN B. OLIVARES

 DIANA JINN SATINA

Noted by:

JESSIE M. CASIA, IE
 Methodology of Research Adviser

Republic of the Philippines
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Website: <http://www.ctu.edu.ph>

Approved by:

BENJAMIN D. RUBIN, CIE, MSIE
Methodology of Research Instructor
Dean, College of Engineering

CURRICULUM VITAE

PERSONAL BACKGROUND

Name: RONA F. CATALIWALAAN

Age: 22

Home Address: Palanas, Alcantara, Cebu

Date of Birth: October 07, 2002

Religion: Roman Catholic

Email Address: rcataliwalaan@gmail.com

Contact Number: 09453587087

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary **Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering**

Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus

Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

Secondary **Alcantara National High School**

Poblacion, Alcantra, Cebu

S.Y. 2020 – 2021

Elementary **Alcantara Central Elementary Cebu**

Poblacion, Alcantra, Cebu

S.Y. 2014 – 2015

